

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS OF MOFSF-2025/ISBN: 978-93-5602-839-5

INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE ON
METAL-ORGANIC
FRAMEWORKS FOR
A SUSTAINABLE
FUTURE

MOFSF-2025

19-20, DECEMBER, 2025 (ONLINE)

Organized by
Department of Chemistry
Government Degree College, Wardhannapet
Warangal District, Kakatiya University,
Telangana State, India-506313

Patron

Smt. A. Sridevasena, IAS
Commissioner of Collegiate Education,
Hyderabad, Government of Telangana

Advisory Board

Prof. D.S.R. Rajender Singh, JD, CCE, Hyderabad
Prof. P. Balabhaskar, RJD, CCE, Hyderabad
Prof. V. Rajendra Prasad, AGO, CCE, Hyderabad
Prof. G. Hanumanthu, Dean of Sciences, Kakatiya University, WGL
Prof. N. Vasudeva Reddy, HOD, Dept. of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, WGL
Prof. T. Savitha Jyostna, BOS Chairperson, Dept. of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, WGL
Prof. S. Jyothi, Principal, University College of Arts & Sciences, Subedari, HNK

Conference Chair

Prof. G. Poshaiiah, Principal,
Govt Degree College, Wardhannapet

Covener/Organizing Secretary

Dr. Srinivas Nerella, Asst. Professor of Chemistry
Govt Degree College, Wardhannapet

College Level Committee

Dr. Ch. Raju, Vice Principal
Dr. G. Rajitha, IQAC Coordinator
Dr. B. Vishnukumar, Academic Coordinator
Dr. M. Reddeppa, Assoc. Professor of History
Dr. A. Madhusudhan Reddy, Asst. Professor of Pol. Science
Dr. V. Sampath Reddy, Asst. Professor of Telugu
Dr. Ch. Snehalatha Reddy, Assoc. Professor of Physics
Dr. K. Sandhya, Asst. Professor of Zoology
Dr. P. E. Sudha Rani, Asst. Professor of English
Dr. B. Swetha, Asst. Professor of Botany
K. Jyosna Devi, Lecturer in Computer Science

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON METAL ORGANIC FRAMEWORKS FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE (MOFSF-2025)

Editor

Dr. Srinivas Nerella

Assistant Professor

Department of Chemistry

Government Degree College, Wardhannapet

Kakatiya University, Warangal

Telangana State. India-506313

Review Committee

Prof. G. Nageswara Rao

Department of Chemistry

Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, A.P.

Prof. Vasam Chandra Sekhar

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry

Telangana University, Nizamabad, T.S.

Published by

Dr. Srinivas Nerella

Department of Chemistry

Government Degree College, Wardhannapet

Warangal District, Kakatiya University

Telangana State, India-506313

INDEX

Sl.No.	Name of the Presenter	Title of the Paper	Page No.
INVITED TALKS			
KL1	Guillaume Maurin	Computation-guided Advances in Metal Organic-Frameworks	8
KL2	Christian Serre	Robust functional Metal Organic Frameworks	9
IL1	Arindam Indra	Organometallic Chemistry in Metal-Organic Framework: Effect on Photocatalytic Energy Conversion	10
IL2	Prof. Koya Prabhakara Rao*	Nano-Structured based 2D-MOF Superhydrophobic Materials for Electro- Chemical Device Applications	11
IL3	Dr. Sudhakar YN	Advanced MOF-Derived Nanocomposite Inks for High-Performance Flexible Microsupercapacitors Toward Sustainable Energy Storage	12
ORAL PRESENTATIONS			
OP1	Das Manmeet Kaur	Designing Dual-Ligand Metal-Organic Frameworks for advanced Mild Steel corrosion inhibition	13
OP2	Ravula Nagaraju	Surface Conductance-Enhanced MOFs-Nanoparticle Hybrids for High Performance Electrocatalytic Water Splitting	14
OP3	Dr. Ganji Saidulu	Cu/C Nanocatalysts Derived from Cu-MOFs for Efficient Conversion of Biomass to value added products	15
OP4	Anushtha Bhardwaj	Reviewing MOF-Perovskite Hybrid Architectures for Enhanced Solar-Driven Hydrogen Production	16
OP5	Dr. Nabanita Pal	Porous Hybrid Zn-Ti Oxide Nanostructures: An environment-friendly Catalyst for Oxidation and Alkylation Reactions	17
OP6	Aabid Abdullah Wani	A Simple Manganese(I) Catalyst for the Efficient and Selective Hydrophosphination of Olefins with PH ₃ , Primary, and Secondary Phosphanes	18
OP7	Shanti Priya Vemuluri	Design, synthesis and anticancer evaluation of various aryl amide derivatives of thiazole-benzothiazole-pyrimidines	19
OP8	Dr. Munagala Alivelu	Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs): Pioneering Work Leading to the 2025 Nobel Prize in Chemistry	20

OP9	Narapureddy Likhitha	Metal–Organic Frameworks (MOFs): A Novel Approach for Enhanced Tuberculosis Drug Delivery	21
OP10	Dr. Ruhi Das	Studies on kinetically active Cerium (IV) species in oxidation of 4-fluorobenzyl alcohol in aqueous micellar sulphuric acid media	22
PAPER PRESENTATIONS			
AS1	Dr. K . Ramesh	Functional Metal–Organic Frameworks for Environmental Protection and Remediation	23
AS2	P. Aruna	Defects and Disorder: Harnessing Imperfections in Porous Framework Materials.	24
AS3	V. Nithin	Design and Synthesis of Nano-sheet Based 2D Composite MOFs for Electro Chemical Devices Applications	25
AS4	P. Ramu	Green Nano-Compositing: Utilizing Bio-Compatible MOFs to Overcome the Barrier Limitations of Corn Starch Packaging	26
AS5	Sandhya Kancharla	Recent Advances in Metal–Organic Framework Adsorbents for Heavy-Metal Removal from Aquatic Environments	27
AS6	Maggidi Vasantha,	Metal-organic frameworks (MOF): Design and Synthesis	28
AS7	B. Ramesh, B. Kavitha	Montmorillonite Clay Supported Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) in Organic Synthesis	29
AS8	Kunsoth Pravalika, Marsakola Annapoorna	MOF-Driven Efficient Gas Storage & Advanced Separation	30
AS9	Pavushetti Soumya	Synergistic Bimetallic MOFs for Sustainable Ibuprofen Remediation	31
AS10	Ch. Snehalatha Reddy	Nano-enabled MOFs solutions for eco-friendly air and water purification	32
AS11	Ganti Jyothi	Catalysis and Environmental Remediation: Challenges and Strategies	33
AS12	B. Venkata Chakravarthi, V Namratha, Tula kavitha	Metal Organic Frameworks for Diverse Applications	34
AS13	Natte Kavitha, T. Savithajyostna	Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs): A review on MOFs Research Leading to the 2025 Nobel Prize in Chemistry	35
AS14	H. Manjunatha	AS14. Synthesis and electrochemical studies of Na ₃ CoCO ₃ PO ₄ as cathode for aqueous rechargeable sodium ion batteries	36

AS15	M. Balaraju	AS15. Smart Drug Delivery Systems: Harnessing Physicochemical Triggers for Controlled Release	37
AS16	T. Jagadish	Synthesis of sulfonated sustainable activated carbon catalysts from Gum Arabic Tree Seed Shell biomass for glycerol esterification	38
AS17	Shanmukhi Jyothi.D, Srikanth.K.	Synthesis and Characterization of Iron Oxide Nano particles via Green Synthesis Technique	39
AS18	Deepak Wadhwa	Novel C-4 Sulfenylated Pyrazoles as α -amylase inhibitors: Insights from <i>in Silico</i> and <i>in vitro</i> studies	40
AS19	J. Uma Rani, P. Jyothi	Biomedical and Drug Delivery Applications of Biodegradable Polymers	41
AS20	C. Raghavender	Rapid Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles with Ginger Waste using Microwave Irradiation	42
AS21	N. Sridhara Devi, M. Narsing Rao, G. Sai Prasad	From Wonder Drugs to Global Threat: The Rise of Antibiotic-Resistant Superbugs	43
AS22	Prasanth Katakam	Development and Validation of an LC–MS/MS Method for Trace-Level Nitrosamine Analysis in Mexiletine Formulations	44
AS23	Santhosh Kumar Ettaboina	Ultra-Sensitive and Green LC-MS/MS Method for Trace-Level Determination of Nitrosamine Drug Substance-Related Impurities in the Anti-Diuretic Drug Furosemide	45
AS24	Tula Kavitha	Synthesis, characterizations, and biological evaluations of 2-(phenyl ((1- phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)methyl)amino) benzenesulfonamide derivatives	46
AS25	Pasam Guruva Reddy	Exploring the extract of <i>Embelia ribes</i> ' berries for its antitumor properties	47
AS26	K. Jagadesh babu	Design, Synthesis and DNA Interaction Studies of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) Complexes with 5-Methyl-o-anisidine Schiff Bases	48
AS27	Satyanarayana Kandala	Synthesis, Characterization, and Thermal Decomposition of Cu(II), Co(II), and Ni(II) Schiff Base Complexes for Metal Oxide Nanoparticle Formation	49
AS28	G. Manasa, Ch. Sunitha	Synthesis and in-vitro screening of Novel 1, 2, 3- Triazole Benzimidazole hybrids	50
AS29	Prabhakar Myadaraveni, Mamatha Kasula	Design and EGFR Targeting of a Furan-Containing Imidazolium Salt for Breast Cancer Therapy: Synthesis, Anticancer Activity, Docking, and DFT Insights	51
AS30	Jeedi Suman, S. Jyothi	Influence of Surface Properties and Metal Interactions in ZnO / Ni / Pd Catalysts for Furfural Aldol Condensation	52
AS31	Vijaykumar Allam, Gavaji Brahmeshwari, Srinivas Nerella	Lawsone as a Precursor for Biologically potent Small Molecules	53

AS32	Goranti Laxmana Rao	DNA Binding cleavage and microbial studies of 4 amino-5-substituted Ary -1,2,4-Triazoles-3-Thione Derivatives and their chelates	54
AS33	S Yuva raju	<i>Butea monosperma</i> -Mediated Silver Nanoparticles: Synthesis, Characterization, and Antimicrobial Activity	55
AS34	Sajal Khatua	<i>Flexible MOFs for Selective Adsorption and Separation of Anions, Dyes, and Indicators in water</i>	56
AS35	Sivakrishnaprasad Satram, Pushpendra Tiwari, Srinivas Nerella	Synthesis and Repurposing Evaluation of Raltegravir analogues as Potential Anticancer Agents	57
AS36	M. Durga Bhavani, K. Narendra	Thermodynamic properties of the binary mixtures of Ethyl phenyl ketone with Alkanediols at different temperatures.	58
AS37	P. Rajani, P. Swathi, K. Bhargavi, and K. Prabhakara Rao	Design and Synthesis of Activated Carbon and Metal Organic Framework-based Composites for High-Performance Super Capacitors	59
AS38	Rajesh. K	Room-Temperature Ethanol Gas Sensing Performance of Lithium-Doped NiO Thin Films Prepared by Spray Pyrolysis	60
AS39	Kalesha Saik, Vijaykumar Allam, Jyothi Prashanth, Ch. N. S. S. Pavan Kumar, Srinivas Nerella	Podophyllotoxin derivatives as potential drugs against cancer treatment	61

Prof. K. Pratap Reddy
Vice-Chancellor

KAKATIYA UNIVERSITY

Accredited with 'A+' Grade by NAAC
Vidyaranyaपुरi, WARANGAL - 506 009
TELANGANA - INDIA

Mobile : 98490 58502 - e-mail: vc@kakatiya.ac.in

No. 70 /NCP/KU/2025

December 16, 2025

MESSAGE

I am delighted to know that the **Department of Chemistry, Government Degree College, Wardhannapet (Kakatiya University)** is organizing the **International Conference on "Metal–Organic Frameworks for a Sustainable Future – MOFSF 2025"** in online mode during **19–20 December 2025**.

Metal–organic frameworks, recognised by the **2025 Nobel Prize in Chemistry**, represent one of the most exciting frontiers in contemporary science. Their unique tunable structures and large internal surface areas open up transformative possibilities in **energy storage and conversion, gas separation, catalysis, environmental remediation, and biomedical applications**. At a time when the world is searching for sustainable, low-carbon solutions, it is heartening that our faculty and students are engaging with such globally relevant technologies.

This conference, with eminent speakers from India and abroad, will provide a rich platform to exchange ideas on MOF design and synthesis, advanced characterisation, and emerging applications. I am particularly pleased that special emphasis is placed on **young researchers, oral presentations, and networking opportunities**, which will nurture a vibrant research culture in our affiliated colleges.

I compliment the **Patron, Advisory Board, Principal, Convener Dr. Srinivas Nerella, and the entire Organising Committee** for their initiative and meticulous planning. I am confident that MOFSF-2025 will stimulate novel collaborations and contribute meaningfully to scientific progress and a more sustainable future.

I extend my warm greetings to all the distinguished speakers and participants and wish the conference grand success.

(Vice-Chancellor)
Kakatiya University

COMMISSIONER OF COLLEGIATE EDUCATION**Government of Telangana, Hyderabad**Office: Prof. Jayashankar Vidya Bhavan, 3rd Floor, Nampally, Hyderabad**Dr. DSR RAJENDER SINGH**

M.Sc. PhD.

Joint Director

I extend my highest appreciation to the organizing committee of the *International Conference on Metal–Organic Frameworks for a Sustainable Future (MOFSF-2025)* for their exemplary efforts in conceptualizing and executing this prestigious event. The meticulous planning, professional coordination, and unwavering commitment demonstrated by the team reflect an exceptional standard of academic leadership.

MOFSF-2025 serves as a distinguished platform for advancing research, fostering international collaboration, and promoting innovation in the field of Metal–Organic Frameworks. The scientific community greatly values such initiatives, which contribute meaningfully to global progress and sustainability.

I really admire the efforts made by the Principal, Convener and staff of Government Degree College, Wardhannapet in organizing an international event on Nobel prize winning discovery. .

I convey my best wishes for the successful conduct of the conference and for its lasting impact on the field.

Prof. DSR Rajendar Singh
Joint Director, CCE
Government of Telangana.

MESSAGE FROM REGIONAL JOINT DIRECTOR, CCE, HYDERABAD

Foreword

It is with immense pleasure and a sense of pride that I extend my warm greetings to all the participants, speakers, and organizers of the International Conference on Metal–Organic Frameworks for a Sustainable Future 2025 (MOFSF-2025).

This conference is timely and significant, coming in the wake of the recognition of Metal–Organic Frameworks (MOFs) with the 2025 Nobel Prize in Chemistry. The award underscores the transformative potential of MOFs in advancing science and technology toward a more sustainable world. MOFs, with their extraordinary porosity, tuneable functionality, and structural versatility, have opened new frontiers in energy storage, environmental remediation, catalysis, biomedical applications, and beyond.

The Department of Chemistry, Government Degree College, Wardhannapet, under Kakatiya University, has taken a commendable initiative in organizing this international gathering in online mode. Such platforms are essential for fostering dialogue, sharing breakthroughs, and building collaborative networks across the globe. By bringing together leading experts like Prof. Christian Serre, Prof. Guillaume Maurin, Prof. Arindam Indra, and Prof. Sudhakar YN, alongside emerging researchers, this conference promises to be a melting pot of ideas and innovations.

I am particularly encouraged by the conference's focus on sustainability—a theme that resonates deeply with global challenges. The scientific themes outlined, from MOF design and energy applications to AI-driven research, reflect the interdisciplinary and future-oriented nature of this field. It is heartening to see young researchers being encouraged through awards and

presentation opportunities, ensuring the continued vibrancy and growth of MOF science.

I congratulate the Conference Chair, Prof. G. Poshalah, the Convener and Organizing Secretary, Dr. Srinivas Nerella, and the entire organizing committee for their vision and effort in curating this meaningful event. I also acknowledge the support of the Commissioner of Collegiate Education, Government of Telangana, and the Advisory Board for their guidance.

To all participants: may your discussions be insightful, your collaborations fruitful, and your contributions impactful. Let this conference be a stepping stone toward a cleaner, greener, and more sustainable future, powered by the remarkable science of Metal–Organic Frameworks.

Wishing MOFSF-2025 great success!

Prof. P. Batabhaskar
Joint Director - II,

Commissioner of Collegiate Education,
Hyderabad, Government of Telangana

Message from the Conference Chair

It is with great pleasure that I welcome you to the *International Conference on Metal–Organic Frameworks for a Sustainable Future (MOFSF-2025)*. This conference represents a collective effort to bring together leading minds from academia, research institutions, and industry to deliberate on the growing impact of Metal–Organic Frameworks in addressing global scientific and societal challenges.

Over the past two decades, Metal–Organic Frameworks have evolved from fundamental structural curiosities to powerful, application-driven materials with relevance in clean energy, environmental sustainability, green catalysis, gas separation, and emerging biomedical technologies. MOFSF-2025 has been envisioned as a forum to critically assess this progress while identifying future directions that can accelerate the translation of MOF research into scalable and sustainable solutions.

The abstracts presented in this volume reflect the depth, rigor, and interdisciplinary character of contemporary MOF research. The strong participation of early-career researchers and students alongside established experts is particularly encouraging and essential for sustaining innovation in this field.

I extend my sincere appreciation to the Dr. Srinivas Nerella, Organizing Secretary and organizing committee, advisory members, reviewers, and all contributors whose commitment has shaped this conference. I am confident that the scientific exchanges during MOFSF-2025 will foster meaningful collaborations and inspire impactful research outcomes.

I thank Commissioner of Collegiate Education, Joint Director, Regional Joint Director, Academic Guidance Officer of Collegiate Education, Hyderabad, Distinguished speakers, delegates for supporting and being a part of MOFSF-2025.

I wish all participants a rewarding and intellectually stimulating conference.

Prof. G. Poshaiyah
Conference Chair
MOFSF-2025

Message from the Convener/Organizing Secretary

It is my great pleasure to present this Book of Abstracts for the *International Conference on Metal–Organic Frameworks for a Sustainable Future (MOFSF-2025)*. The conference has been thoughtfully designed to provide a vibrant international platform for researchers, academicians, industry professionals, and young scientists to share recent advances and future perspectives in the rapidly evolving field of Metal–Organic Frameworks.

Metal–Organic Frameworks have emerged as a versatile class of functional materials with transformative potential in gas storage and separation, catalysis, energy applications, environmental remediation, and biomedical sciences. In the context of global sustainability challenges, MOF research plays a crucial role in bridging fundamental science with real-world solutions, aligning strongly with global sustainability goals.

The abstracts compiled in this volume reflect the scientific diversity, innovation, and interdisciplinary nature of the conference. Contributions from distinguished experts, early-career researchers, and students highlight both fundamental insights and application-oriented research, underscoring the dynamic growth of this field.

I sincerely thank the authors for their valuable submissions, the reviewers for their meticulous evaluation, and the advisory and organizing committees for their unwavering support. I also acknowledge the dedication of the technical and administrative teams whose efforts have ensured the successful organization of MOFSF-2025.

I earnestly thank Commissioner of Collegiate Education, Joint Director, Regional Joint Director, Academic Guidance Officer of Collegiate Education, Hyderabad, Conference Chair, Prof. G. Poshaiyah, Principal, GDC, Wardhannapet, Distinguished speakers, delegates and fellow colleagues at our college.

Dr. Srinivas Nerella
Convener/Organizing Secretary
MOFSF-2025

KEYNOTE LECTURE-I

Computation-guided Advances in Metal-Organic-Frameworks

Guillaume Maurin*

ICGM, Université de Montpellier, CNRS, ENSCM, Montpellier 34293, France

Institut Universitaire de France (IUF), France

Email: guillaume.maurin1@umontpellier.fr

Abstract: MOFs offer unparalleled structural tunability for energy and environmental applications. Yet, their vast chemical and structural diversity make exhaustive experimental screening unfeasible. Computational modelling, empowered by machine-learning (ML) methods now provides a powerful route to accelerate discovery and optimization. Our recent work shows how Machine Learning Potentials (MLPs) bridge quantum accuracy and large-scale efficiency, enabling predictive modelling of flexible frameworks that undergo structural transitions under external stimuli. In particular, MLPs capture strong host–guest interactions in MOFs with open metal sites, inaccessible to traditional force fields, allowing accurate predictions of adsorption and mechanical behaviour. We also explore mixed-matrix membranes (MMMs) combining MOFs with polymers for gas separation. Through multiscale simulations, we reveal how polymer rigidity and MOF surface chemistry control interfacial pore structure and, consequently, gas transport. Importantly, we show that pore shape, beyond size, governs molecular selectivity. Together, these computational advances establish a rational design framework for next-generation MOFs and hybrid membranes, bridging atomistic insight with real-world performance.

KEYNOTE LECTURE-II

Robust functional Metal Organic Frameworks

Christian Serre

Institut des Matériaux Poreux de Paris (IMAP)

Ecole Normale Supérieure - ESPCI Paris, CNRS, PSL university,

24 rue Lhomond/10 rue Vauquelin, 75005 Paris, France.

Contact: christian.serre@ens.psl.eu

Abstract: The importance of the so-called Metal-Organic Frameworks or MOF has been recently recognised by the Nobel committee with the award given to prof. Robson, Kitagawa and Yaghi. I will briefly introduce what are MOF and the main reasons behind this prestigious award. Then, I will show who, at the Institut des Matériaux Poreux de Paris, we have devoted a long-term effort to the synthesis and structural characterization of new functional, robust, porous (and scalable) MOFs based on high valence transition metal cations constructed from various types of ligands (carboxylates, phosphonates, phenolates).[1] Al or Fe carboxylates based MOFs, whose chemistry in solution is “easier” to control, have been extensively explored for gas phase separation or the capture of CO₂, assisted eventually by AI,[2] as well as, more recently, for the capture of air pollutants.[3] Other more chemically challenging systems, such as Ti-MOFs, have been investigated due to their unique photocatalytic properties.[4] Zr or Ce(IV) MOFs have been explored as alternative MOFs catalysts, including their preparation under green and mild synthetic routes.[5] Finally, I will briefly show how we developed the synthesis at nanoscale of biocompatible Fe-MOFs in a view of biomedical applications.[6]

Keywords: Metal Organic Frameworks, metal carboxylates, indoor air quality, photocatalysis, composites

References

- [1] A. Y. Ozturk et al *Adv. Mater.*, **2025**, adma.202411359R2
- [2] (a) B. Chen et al, *Adv. Sci.*, **2024**, 10.1002/advs.202401070; (b) C. Charalambous, et al., *Nature*, **2024**, 632, 89–94; doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07683-8
- [3] (a) N. Sadovnik, et al, *Nat. Comm.*, **2024**, doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-53572-z; (b) M. Daturi et al, *Adv. Mater.* **2024**, doi.org/10.1002/adma.202403053
- [4] A. Garcia-Baldovi et al., *Energy Environ. Science*, **2023**, *16*, 167-177, doi.org/10.1039/d2ee02258c
- [5] S. Dai et al *Nat. Comm.*, **2024**, *15*, 3334, doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-47426-x
- [6] Z. Lu, *Adv. Healthcare Mat.*, **2024**, doi.org/10.1002/adhm.202402418

Invited Lecture-I

Organometallic Chemistry in Meatal-Organic Framework: Effect on Photocatalytic Energy Conversion

Arindam Indra*

Department of Chemistry, IIT (BHU), Varanasi, UP-221005, INDIA

E-mail: arindam.chy@iitbhu.ac.in

Abstract: The photocatalytic energy conversion processes like H_2 and O_2 evolution, and CO_2 reduction reactions require an efficient photocatalyst to absorb light in the visible region.¹ In this talk, the use of CdS nanorods as the photocatalyst for the different energy conversion processes will be described. Although the bandgap and band positions of CdS are suitable for the photocatalytic H_2 evolution and CO_2 reduction, the high charger combination rate than the surface redox reaction(s) make the process challenging.² In this context, the cocatalyst plays an important role in charge separation and transport and the minimization of charge recombination.¹ Herein, we will explore the designing of different metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) as the efficient cocatalysts based on the principles of organometallic chemistry. The cocatalytic activities of different MOFs, viz., CoFe–Prussian blue analog (CoFe–PBA) and CoFe–nitroprusside (CoFe–NP) integrated on the surface of CdS nanorods will be demonstrated for the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution reaction (Figure 1).³ The π -acidity of $-CN$ vs. $-NO$ will be explored in the cocatalyst structure for a better separation and transport of the photogenerated charge carriers and hence an improved photocatalytic activity.⁴⁻⁵ In addition, the effect of the spin state modulation of cobalt ion in CoCo-PBA will be described to control the photocatalytic activity and product selectivity for CO_2 reduction with CoCo-PBA@CdS.⁶ The concept will be further extended to photoelectrochemical water oxidation with CoCo-PBA@BiVO₄.⁷

References:

(1) A. K. Singh, C. Das, A. Indra, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2022**, 465, 214516. (2) L. Cheng, Q. Xiang, Y. Liao and H. Zhang, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2018**, 11, 1362–1391. (3) A. K. Singh, A. Jaryal, S. K. Patel, D. Kumar, E. S. S. Iyer, K. Kailasam, A. Indra, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2023**, 11, 16724-16733. (4) B. Singh, Y. Arya, G. K. Lahiri, A. Indra, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2025**, 523, 216288. (5) B. Singh, P. Mannu, Y. C. Huang, R. Prakash, S. Shen, C. L. Dong, A. Indra, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2022**, 61, e202211585. (6) and (7) Indra et al. Unpublished work

Invited Lecture-II

Nano-Structured based 2D-MOF Superhydrophobic Materials for Electro-Chemical Device Applications

Prof. Koya Prabhakara Rao*

New Generation Materials Lab (NGML), Department of Chemistry, School of Applied Science and Humanities, Vignan's Foundation for Science Technology and Research, Vadlamudi-522 213, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail: drkpr_sh@vignan.ac.in

Abstract: Porous coordination polymers (PCPs), also known as metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), have emerged as potential materials of the decade, particularly for gas storage, separation, catalysts, sensors, etc. However, MOFs in the literature were mostly unstable regarding moisture and bulk water. Besides these traditional MOFs, we have designed and synthesized an organic-rich, low-density-based ligand and converted them into MOFs showing exceptional superhydrophobic properties.¹ In the present study, we achieved MOFs /nanosheet-based superhydrophobic MOFs and nanoparticle-embedded superhydrophobic MOFs for electro-catalytical water-splitting applications.² Here we report on metallic and bimetallic MOF-based electro-catalysts, achieved by the solvothermal method. All of them were characterized by PXRD, SEM, TEM, EDX, etc. The electro-catalytical analyses of water splitting studies on these MOFs demonstrate strong electro-catalytic capabilities for hydrogen evolution reactions (HERs)³ and oxygen evolution reactions (OER). This study presents a simple approach for producing high-performance MOF-based electro-catalysts with numerous exposed active sites derived from metallic and bimetallic MOFs.

Invited Lecture-III

Advanced MOF-Derived Nanocomposite Inks for High-Performance Flexible Microsupercapacitors Toward Sustainable Energy Storage

Dr. Sudhakar YN

Department of Chemistry, MAHE, Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal, India

Abstract: Flexible and wearable electronics are driving a paradigm shift in portable energy storage, demanding miniaturized devices with enhanced electrochemical performance and mechanical robustness. This talk presents *two complementary strategies* for engineering MOF-based nanocomposite inks optimized for high-performance flexible microsupercapacitors, with a focus on sustainable device fabrication and application.

First, zeolitic imidazolate framework (ZIF-67)-derived Co_3O_4 nanostructures were integrated with reduced graphene oxide (rGO) to formulate a conductive ink suitable for screen-printed microsupercapacitors. Response surface methodology (RSM) was employed to optimize the calcination temperature, revealing that a $550\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ treatment yields a highly porous $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{rGO}$ network with superior conductivity and electroactive surface area. The resulting symmetric and asymmetric microsupercapacitors demonstrated excellent areal capacitance (up to $\sim 1220\text{ mF cm}^{-2}$), high energy and power densities, and outstanding cycling stability ($>94\%$ retention after 10 000 cycles), highlighting the potential of MOF-derived composites for durable energy storage applications.

Second, a Ni-MOF/CuSe nanocomposite ink was formulated to further improve device flexibility and foldability. Blending Ni-MOF with copper selenide (CuSe) enabled effective screen printing of foldable micro-energy storage devices that delivered high areal capacitance and competitive energy/power densities. Incorporation into a 3D enclosure configuration significantly enhanced performance metrics while maintaining strong mechanical durability and capacitance retention during bending tests. Together, these MOF-derived conductive inks represent scalable strategies to address current limitations in flexible energy storage systems, offering pathways toward sustainable, high-performance microsupercapacitors suitable for next-generation portable and wearable technologies.

OP1. Designing Dual-Ligand Metal-Organic Frameworks for advanced Mild Steel corrosion inhibition

Das Manmeet Kaur¹, Sheetal¹, Sanjeeve Thakur¹, Ashish Kumar Singh^{1,2}

¹Department of Chemistry, Netaji Subhas University of Technology, Dwarka Sector 3, New Delhi-110078, India

²Department of Chemistry, Hansraj College, Delhi University, New Delhi-110063, India
E-mail: ps.sharma9545@gmail.com

Abstract: The present work focuses on the design and evaluation of dual-ligand transition-metal metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) as corrosion inhibitors for mild steel. A series of cobalt- and nickel-based MOFs incorporating trimesic acid and quinoxaline were synthesized and characterized using X-ray diffraction and spectroscopic techniques. Their corrosion inhibition performance in brine solution was assessed through electrochemical measurements and complemented by surface analyses.

The dual-ligand MOFs exhibited significantly enhanced inhibition efficiency compared to their single-ligand counterparts under identical conditions. The improved performance is attributed to the synergistic interaction between the two organic ligands and the metal centers, which promotes robust surface adsorption and effectively suppresses corrosion processes. Overall, the study demonstrates that dual-ligand MOFs serve as highly effective corrosion inhibitors for mild steel in brine environments.

References

1. Zhang, Y., Wang, J., Zhao, S., Serdechnova, M., Blawert, C., Wang, H., ... & Chen, F. (2021). Double-ligand strategy to construct an inhibitor-loaded Zn-MOF and its corrosion protection ability for aluminum alloy 2A12. *ACS applied materials & interfaces*, 13(43), 51685-51694.
2. Abd El Aziz, S. F., Etaiw, S. E. H., & Sobhy, S. (2022). Metal-organic frameworks based on heterocyclic ligands and some transition metals as effective carbon steel corrosion inhibitors in aqueous environment. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 348, 118402.

OP2. Surface Conductance-Enhanced MOFs-Nanoparticle Hybrids for High Performance Electrocatalytic Water Splitting

Ravula Nagaraju and Koya Prabhakara Rao*

New Generation Materials Lab (NGML), Department of Chemistry, School of Applied Science and Humanities, Vignan's Foundation for Science Technology and Research, Vadlamudi-522 213, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India

nagarajravula4@gmail.com and drkpr_sh@vignan.ac.in

Abstract: Porous coordination polymers (PCPs), which are also known as metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), have emerged as potential materials of the decade, particularly for gas storage, separation, catalysts, sensors, etc. However, MOFs existing in the literature were mostly unstable with respect to moisture and bulk water. Besides these traditional MOFs, we have designed and synthesized an organic-rich, low-density-based ligand and converted them into MOFs showing exceptional superhydrophobic properties.¹⁻³ In the present study, we achieved a few nanosheet-based superhydrophobic MOFs⁴ and also nanoparticle-embedded superhydrophobic MOFs for the electrocatalytical applications for water-splitting applications.⁴ Here we report on metallic and bimetallic metal-organic framework-based electrocatalysts, **RuO₂@Zn-BTMB (1)**, **RuO₂@Zn-Co-BTMB (2)**, and **RuO₂@Zn-Ni-BTMB (3)**, achieved by Sono-Chemical method. All of them were characterized by PXRD, SEM, TEM, EDX, etc. The electro-catalytical analyses of water splitting studies on these three PCPs in alkaline environments demonstrate strong electrocatalytic capabilities for hydrogen evolution processes (HERs) oxygen evolution processes (OERs). This study presents a simple approach for producing high-performance PCP-based electrocatalysts with numerous exposed active sites derived from metallic and bimetallic PCPs.

References:

1. K. Prabhakara Rao, M. Higuchi, K. Sumida J. Duan, S. Furakawa and S. Kitagawa, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 53 (2014), 8225.
2. K. Prabhakara Rao, M. Higuchi, J. Suryachandram and S. Kitagawa, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 140 (2018), 13786.
3. J. Suryachandram, R. Nagaraju, J. N. Behera, K Prabhakara Rao*, *Inorg. Chem.* 61 (2022), 14344.
J. Suryachandram, R. Nagaraju, K Prabhakara Rao*, *et al ACS Applied Energy*, (2025) 8(8), 5291

OP3. Cu/C Nanocatalysts Derived from Cu-MOFs for Efficient Conversion of Biomass to value added products

Dr.G.Saidulu^a, Dr. K.Ramesh^a, Dr. G. Kumaraswamy^b

^aDepartment of chemistry, Chaitanya Bharathi Institute of Technology, Hyderabad,Telangana

^bDepartment of physics and chemistry, Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana.

Corresponding author E-mail: saiduluganji@gmail.com

Abstract: The demand for sustainable catalytic technologies has spurred growing interest in metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) as precursors for advanced functional materials. In this work, Cu/C nanocatalysts were developed through controlled carbonization of a Cu-BTC MOF synthesized from copper nitrate and benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylic acid. The resulting materials feature uniformly dispersed Cu nanoparticles embedded in a porous, partially graphitized carbon matrix. XRD, SEM, and TEM analyses confirmed the structural transformation from MOF to Cu/C, preservation of the polyhedral morphology, and formation of well-distributed nanosized copper domains. These characteristics collectively enhanced electron transfer and substrate accessibility, leading to high catalytic activity, selectivity, and stability in the hydrogenation of biomass-derived levulinic acid to γ -valerolactone. The strong metal–carbon interaction and hierarchical porosity supported efficient hydrogen activation, highlighting the promise of MOF-derived Cu/C catalysts for green chemical processes. This study demonstrates a strategic pathway for designing high-performance catalysts and contributes to advancing sustainable biomass-valorization technologies.

OP4. Reviewing MOF–Perovskite Hybrid Architectures for Enhanced Solar-Driven Hydrogen Production

Anushtha Bhardwaj*, Rohit Shrivastav, Manju Srivastava

Solar Hydrogen Lab, Department of Chemistry, Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Dayalbagh, Agra-282005, INDIA
E-mail : anushthabhardwaj1022@gmail.com , rsmanjusrivastava@gmail.com

Abstract: Solar-driven photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting has emerged as a highly promising route for addressing the global energy crisis by enabling sustainable hydrogen production. Recent research has clearly illustrated the potential of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) and perovskites owing to their structural uniformity and synthetic adaptability. The combination of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) with perovskites for photoelectrochemical (PEC) systems can enhance and expand light absorption while optimizing charge transfer kinetics, hence fulfilling the criteria for an innovative photoelectrode in PEC water splitting applications. Their highly crystalline structure enhances charge separation efficiency, mitigating electron-hole pair recombination, which is a key limitation in current PEC performance [1,2].

A significantly large surface area, a homogenous adjustable pore structure with accessible active sites, is particularly advantageous in this context. Furthermore, MOFs are optimal for use as sacrificial templates in the synthesis of functional materials derived from earth-abundant transition metals [3]. In this work, we investigate the synergistic behaviour of MOF–perovskite hybrid structures for solar-driven hydrogen evolution. Comprehensive results and mechanistic insights from this study will be presented in detail.

Keywords: metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), Perovskites, photoelectrochemical (PEC) etc.

References

1. Tey, Quan Yee, et al. "Next-generation perovskite-metal–organic framework (MOF) hybrids in photoelectrochemical water splitting: a path to green hydrogen solutions." *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 13.13 (2025): 9005-9038.
2. Li, Jiaming, et al. "Recent research progress of MOFs-based heterostructures for photocatalytic hydrogen evolution." *Chemical Engineering Journal* 498 (2024): 155194.
3. Dutta, Runjhun, et al. "MOFs in photoelectrochemical water splitting: New horizons and challenges." *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 47.8 (2022): 5192-5210.

OP5. Porous Hybrid Zn-Ti Oxide Nanostructures: An environment-friendly Catalyst for Oxidation and Alkylation Reactions

Nabanita Pal*

Department of Physics and Chemistry, Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology, Gandipet, Hyderabad 500075, Telangana State, India

Email id: nabanitapal_chem@mgit.ac.in

Abstract: A simple porous hybrid zinc-titanium oxide nanoparticle has been synthesized in a unique method based on evaporation-induced self-assembly (EISA) sol-gel route using Pluronic triblock copolymer P123 as a template. Powder XRD data reveals that the composite material displays ZnTiO₃/TiO₂ phases. Morphology, composition, porosity, nanostructure and thermal stability have been thoroughly investigated using small angle powder XRD, FE SEM-EDS, TEM, N₂ sorption, FT IR and TG-DTA techniques. The sample shows a high BET surface area of 231 m²g⁻¹ with a typical mesopore diameter (~ 5 nm) arising mostly from interparticle void space. This Zn-Ti hybrid oxide showed catalytic bifunctional activity for Friedel-Craft benzylation of aromatics using benzyl chloride as well as partial oxidation of olefins under mild environment-friendly reaction conditions using dilute aqueous H₂O₂ as oxidant.

Keywords: Catalysis, mixed oxide, porous, bifunctional.

References:

N. Pal, D. Chakraborty, A. Bhaumik, M. Ali, J. Inorg. Organometallic Polymers Mater., 2022, 32, 3141-3152 (<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10904-022-02347-4>)

OP6. A Simple Manganese(I) Catalyst for the Efficient and Selective Hydrophosphination of Olefins with PH₃, Primary, and Secondary Phosphanes

Aabid A. Wani,^[a,b] Juan José Gamboa Carballo,^[a,] Harikrishnan Jayaprakash,^[a] Michael Wörle,^[a] Anna Widera,^[a] Antonio Togni,^{*[a]} Hansjörg Grützmacher,^{*[a]}
 [a] Dr. A. Wani, J. J. Gamboa-Carballo, Dr. H. Jayaprakash, Dr. M. Wörle, Dr. A. Widera, Prof. em. Dr. A. Togni, Prof. Dr. H. Grützmacher.

[a] Department of Chemistry and Applied Biosciences, ETH,
 Vladimir-Prelog-Weg 1, CH-8093 Zurich, Switzerland

[b] School of Pharmacy, GITAM University, Rudraram, Telangana 502329, India
 E-mail: antonio.togni@inorg.chem.ethz.ch ; hgruetzmacher@ethz.ch

Abstract: A tridentate ligand **L** with a P,NH,N donor motif was synthesized in few steps from commercially available precursors. Upon reaction with [MnBr(CO)₅], an octahedral 18- electron complex [Mn(CO)₃(L)]Br (**1**) is obtained in which **L** adopts a facial arrangement. After deprotonation of the NH group in the cationic complex unit, a neutral Mn(I) amide complex [Mn(CO)₂(L-H)] (**2**) is formed under loss of CO. Rearrangement of **L-H** leads to a trigonal bipyramidal structure in which the P and N donor centers are in *trans* position. Further deprotonation of **2** results in a dep-blue anionic complex fragment [Mn(CO)₂(L-2H)]⁻ (**3**). DFT calculations and a QTAIM analysis show that the amide **2** contains a Mn–N bond with partial double bond character and **3** an aromatic MnN₂C₂ ring. The anion [Mn(CO)₂(L-2H)]⁻ reacts with Ph₂PH to give a phosphido complex, which serves as phosphide transfer reagent to activated olefins. But the catalytic activity is low. However, the neutral amide complex **2** is an excellent catalyst and with loadings as low as 0.04 mol%, turn over frequencies of >40'000 h⁻¹ can be achieved. Furthermore, secondary and primary alkyl phosphines as well as PH₃ can be added in a catalytic hydrophosphination reaction to a wide range of activated olefins such as α,β-unsaturated aldehydes, ketones, esters, and nitriles. But also, vinyl pyridine and some styrene derivatives are converted into the corresponding phosphanes (Figure 1).

Figure 1: A Mn(I) amido complex with a tridentate P,N,N ligand.

1. A.A. Wani, J.J.G. Carballo, H. Jayaprakash, M. Wörle, A. Widera, A. Togni, and H. Grützmacher, *Chem. - Eur. J.* **2024**, 30, e202303848.

OP7. Design, synthesis and anticancer evaluation of various aryl amide derivatives of thiazole-benzothiazole-pyrimidines

Shanti Priya Vemuluri^a, Vijaya Laxmi Somarapu^a

^a Department of Chemistry, Palamuru University, Mahabubnagar, Telangana 509001, India

Abstract: We have developed a new series of various aryl amide derivatives of thiazole-benzothiazole-pyrimidines (**13a-j**). Their chemical structures were characterized by ¹HNMR, ¹³CNMR and mass spectral data. Further, the *in vitro* anticancer properties of newly derivative compounds **13a-j** were investigated against four human cancer cell lines including MCF-7 (breast cancer), A549 (lung cancer), Colo-205 (colon cancer) & A2780 (ovarian cancer) by employing of MTT assay, and were compared with etoposide which is used as standard reference. . Most of the tested compounds were displayed moderate to good anticancer activities than etoposide. The *in vitro* assay results indicated that compounds **13a**, **13b**, **13c** and **13d** were possessed more potent activity as compared with standard. One of the compounds like **13a** displayed superior anticancer activity.

OP8. Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs): Pioneering Work Leading to the 2025 Nobel Prize in Chemistry

Munagala Aivelu^{a*}

^aDept of Chemistry, Govt. Degree College, Gajwel, Telangana 506370, India

Email: munagalaalivelu@gmail.com

Abstract: Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) are crystalline materials composed of metal ions interconnected by organic linkers, forming highly porous three-dimensional structures. These frameworks exhibit remarkable properties such as tunable porosity, large surface areas, and structural versatility, enabling applications in gas storage, catalysis, drug delivery, and environmental remediation. The 2025 Nobel Prize in Chemistry was awarded jointly to Richard Robson, Susumu Kitagawa, and Omar M. Yaghi for their independent yet complementary contributions that established the foundations of MOF chemistry. Robson pioneered the first three-dimensional coordination polymers, Kitagawa demonstrated porous and flexible frameworks capable of gas adsorption, and Yaghi developed the concept of reticular chemistry, enabling systematic design of stable and functional MOFs. This review summarizes the historical development, structural features, key properties, and wide-ranging applications of MOFs, highlighting the scientific impact of these discoveries. The paper also discusses current trends and future perspectives, emphasizing the potential of MOFs in sustainable technologies and advanced materials research.

OP9. Metal–Organic Frameworks (MOFs): A Novel Approach for Enhanced Tuberculosis Drug Delivery

Narapureddy Likhitha, Ananthagiri Sai Sriya, Sahitya Madhinni & Syeda Amena Kausar*
Department of Genetics & Biotechnology, Veeranari Chakali Iamma Women's University,

Hyderabad, Telangana 500095, India.

Corresponding Author's Email address: amenaucw@gmail.com

Abstract: Tuberculosis (TB) remains a pressing global health issue characterized by lengthy treatment regimens, high pill burden, and the emergence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains. Conventional anti-TB therapies are limited by poor bioavailability, systemic toxicity, and suboptimal delivery to pulmonary infection sites. Metal–Organic Frameworks (MOFs), a class of crystalline porous materials composed of metal ions and organic linkers, have emerged as promising platforms for efficient drug delivery. Their tunable pore architecture, high surface area, and exceptional loading capacity enable controlled encapsulation and sustained release of anti-TB agents. Biocompatible MOFs, particularly those based on iron (Fe) and zirconium (Zr), demonstrate potential for pulmonary administration due to their stability, biodegradability, and compatibility with inhalable formulations. These nanocarriers enhance macrophage uptake, co-deliver synergistic drug combinations, and maintain therapeutic concentrations at infection foci, thereby improving treatment outcomes and patient compliance. By reducing systemic toxicity and mitigating the development of drug resistance, MOF-based delivery systems represent a transformative step toward more targeted and effective TB management. This review explores current advances in MOF synthesis, functionalization, and application in tuberculosis drug delivery, highlighting their potential to revolutionize future anti-TB therapy.

Keywords: Metal–Organic Frameworks, Tuberculosis, Controlled release, Pulmonary drug delivery, Nanocarriers, Drug resistance, Targeted therapy

OP10. Studies on kinetically active Cerium (IV) species in oxidation of 4-fluorobenzyl alcohol in aqueous micellar sulphuric acid media

Dr. Ruhi Das

Department of Chemistry, Bolpur College, Birbhum, Pin 731204, WB, India

Abstract: Kinetics of the oxidation of 4-fluorobenzyl alcohol by Ce(IV) in aqueous sulfuric acid media have been investigated both in the absence and presence of the cationic surfactant, N-cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) and the anionic surfactant, sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS). Under the conditions $[4\text{-fluorobenzyl alcohol}] \gg [\text{Ce(IV)}]$, the reaction exhibits first-order kinetics both in $[\text{Ce(IV)}]$ and $[4\text{-fluorobenzyl alcohol}]$. The rate retarding effect of HSO_4^- has been analysed and it has been noted that both $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{2+}$ and $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ are kinetically active but their relative contribution depends on the nature of the 4-fluorobenzyl alcohol and surfactant. The different rate constants in the presence and absence of surfactants have been determined with the corresponding activation parameters. SDS has been found to accelerate the rate process. CPC has been found to retard the process, the rate is more or less insensitive to CPC. All these findings, including the micellar effects, have been interpreted in terms of the proposed reaction mechanism and partitioning behaviour of the different kinetically active species of Ce(IV) between the aqueous and pseudomicellar phases.

Keywords: Cerium (IV), 4-fluorobenzyl alcohol, oxidation, micellar effect, surfactants.

References:

- [1] Das, A.K. (2000) Fundamental concepts of inorganic chemistry, CBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, India., Part II, p. 753.
- [2] Das, A.K. (1996) J. Chem. Res (S). 184. J. Chem. Res. (M)., 1023.
- [3] Saha, P.N., Mondal, S.K., Kar, D., Das, M., Das, A.K. and Mohanty, R.K.
- [4]

AS1. Functional Metal–Organic Frameworks for Environmental Protection and Remediation

K.Ramesh^a, G.Saidulu^a, G. Kumaraswamy^b

^a Department of chemistry, Chaitanya Bharathi Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India-500075

^b Department of physics and chemistry, Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, Telangana, India--500075

Corresponding author E-mail: kramesh_chm@cbit.ac.in

Abstract: Metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) have emerged as highly versatile materials for addressing key environmental challenges due to their exceptionally high surface area, tunable pore structures, and customizable chemical functionality. Their ability to selectively capture greenhouse gases such as CO₂ and CH₄ positions them as promising candidates for carbon capture and air purification. In water treatment, MOFs enable efficient removal of heavy metals, dyes, pharmaceuticals, and emerging contaminants through selective adsorption and catalytic degradation. Additionally, their unique optical and structural properties allow for sensitive detection of pollutants in environmental sensing applications. Ongoing advancements in MOF stability, scalable synthesis, and integration into membranes and composites continue to enhance their practical deployment, highlighting their strong potential in driving sustainable solutions for cleaner air, water, and environmental remediation.

AS2. Defects and Disorder: Harnessing Imperfections in Porous Framework Materials

P. Aruna, Assistant Professor of Physics, Pingle Government College for Women(A),
Waddepally, Hanamkonda

Email: aruna1.physics@gmail.com

Abstract: Harnessing Imperfections in Porous Framework Materials. The conventional pursuit of materials science emphasizes perfect, long-range crystalline order. However, in the realm of highly porous Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) and Covalent-Organic Frameworks (COFs), the presence of defects and disorder has emerged as a powerful paradigm for rational materials design, moving from structural impediment to functional opportunity. This work reviews the strategic concept of defect engineering—the deliberate creation and control of structural imperfections—to unlock and enhance physicochemical properties in these materials. We delineate common defect types, such as missing linker (ML) vacancies and disordered secondary building units (SBUs) in MOFs, and incomplete cyclization or stacking faults in COFs. Critically, these imperfections introduce unsaturated metal sites, open pore channels, and enhanced chemical accessibility, dramatically improving performance in key applications. We highlight recent advances in utilizing defective frameworks to boost catalytic activity, increase gas adsorption capacity and selectivity, and tune electrical conductivity and mechanical stability. Finally, we discuss the challenging state-of-the-art characterization techniques (e.g., advanced NMR, in-situ microscopy, and computational modelling) essential for linking a defect's microscopic structure to the material's macroscopic function, paving the way for the next generation of highly functional porous materials.

Keywords: Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs), Covalent-Organic Frameworks (COFs), Porous Materials, Hybrid Frameworks, Nanoporous Materials

AS3. Design and Synthesis of Nano-sheet Based 2D Composite MOFs for Electro Chemical Devices Applications

V.Nithin, R. Nagaraju, and K. Prabhakara Rao*

New Generation Materials Lab (NGML), Department of Chemistry, School of Applied Science and Humanities, Vignan's Foundation for Science Technology and Research (VFSTR) (Deemed to be University), Vadlamudi-522 213, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India
drkpr_sh@vignan.ac.in

Abstract: Porous coordination polymers (PCPs), which also known as metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are emerged as potential materials of the decade, particularly for gas storage, separation, catalysts and sensors etc. However, PCPs/MOFs existing in the literature were mostly instability with respect to moisture and bulk water. Besides these traditional PCPs/MOFs, we have been designed and synthesized an organic rich low density-based ligands and converted them in to PCPs/MOFs shown exceptional superhydrophobic properties¹⁻⁴. In the present study, we achieved few 2D-Nano-sheet based superhydrophobic MOFs and Mxenes are made in the form of composite materials for various electrochemical Device applications such as LIBs, super capacitors and electro-catalysts for the water splitting applications. This study presents a simple approach for producing high-performance PCP-based catalysts with numerous exposed active sites derived from metallic and bimetallic PCPs.

References:

1. K. Prabhakara Rao, M. Higuchi, K. Sumida J. Duan, S. Furakawa and S. Kitagawa, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 53 (2014), 8225.
2. K. Prabhakara Rao, M. Higuchi, J. Suryachandram and S. Kitagawa, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 140 (2018), 13786.
3. J. Suryachandram, R. Nagaraju, K Prabhakara Rao*, *et al ACS Applied Energy*, (2025) 8(8), 5291–5298.

AS4. Green Nano-Compositing: Utilizing Bio-Compatible MOFs to Overcome the Barrier Limitations of Corn Starch Packaging

P. Ramu

Department of Chemistry

Girraj Government College (A), Nizamabad, Telangana, India

Email: perumandlaramu@gmail.com

Abstract: The inherent hydrophilicity and poor gas barrier properties of corn starch-based bioplastics present significant challenges for their application in sustainable packaging. This work addresses these limitations through a green nano-compositing strategy, integrating bio-compatible metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) as functional nano-fillers. We selected and synthesized non-toxic, water-stable MOFs, specifically focusing on zeolitic imidazolate framework-8 (ZIF-8) and a calcium-based MOF using citric acid, chosen for their potential biocompatibility and scalable aqueous synthesis routes. These MOFs were incorporated into a plasticized corn starch matrix via a simple, solvent-blending method to form homogeneous composite films.

This study successfully demonstrates that green nano-compositing with tailored, bio-compatible MOFs is a powerful and sustainable methodology to engineer corn starch packaging materials with high-barrier and robust mechanical properties, thereby bridging the performance gap with conventional plastics and advancing the viability of bioplastics for practical packaging applications.

AS5. Recent Advances in Metal–Organic Framework Adsorbents for Heavy-Metal Removal from Aquatic Environments

Sandhya Kancharla

*Govt. Degree College, wardhannapet,
Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana, India
Email: sandhyakancharla2013@gmail.com*

Abstract: Metal–Organic Frameworks (MOFs) have gained significant attention as advanced adsorbent materials for heavy-metal removal due to their large surface area, structural tunability, and strong adsorption affinity. Rapid urbanization and industrial expansion have intensified heavy-metal contamination in water systems, creating an urgent need for efficient purification technologies. Although several treatment methods, including ion exchange, precipitation, and membrane filtration, are available, adsorption is preferred for its simplicity, low operational cost, and high efficiency. Recent investigations demonstrate that MOFs exhibit exceptional selectivity and capacity for removing heavy metals, organic dyes, and persistent organic contaminants. However, challenges such as limited water stability, high regeneration costs, and scalability issues hinder their widespread application. This review presents current advancements in water-stable and high-performance MOF adsorbents, emphasizing key operational parameters such as pH, initial metal concentration, and MOF dosage. Additionally, hybrid treatment strategies that integrate MOF-based adsorption with complementary techniques are discussed. The review highlights adsorption mechanisms, identifies critical limitations, and outlines future research directions for developing scalable and robust MOF-based water-treatment systems.

Keywords: MOFs, heavy metals, adsorption, water treatment, wastewater, hybrid methods, remediation.

AS6. Metal-organic frameworks (MOF): Design and Synthesis

Maggidi Vasantha, * N.Chandra Kiran

Dept. of Chemistry, Palamuru University, Mahabubnagar, Telangana, India

Abstract: Metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) are highly tunable porous materials formed through the coordination of metal ions or clusters with organic linkers, enabling precise control over pore structure, stability, and functionality. Advances in synthesis—including solvothermal, microwave-assisted, mechanochemical, and electrochemical methods—have improved efficiency, scalability, and structural diversity. Developments in reticular chemistry, isorecticular design, post-synthetic modification, and metal-site activation have further expanded MOF capabilities, particularly in gas storage, separation, and catalysis. Despite significant progress, challenges in large-scale, cost-effective production and long-term stability remain. Emerging computational and AI-driven approaches offer promising pathways to optimize MOF design for energy, environmental, and biomedical applications.

Keywords: Metal–organic frameworks (MOFs), porous materials, reticular chemistry, microwave-assisted synthesis, mechanochemistry, stability, computational design, artificial intelligence.

AS7. Montmorillonite Clay Supported Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) in Organic Synthesis

B. Ramesh,* B. Kavitha#

**Government Degree & PG College, Jammikunta, Dist.
Karimnagar E-mail: drbodduramesh@gmail.com*

*#Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana
E-mail: drkavithachem@gmail.com*

Abstract: Anchored catalysts combine the chemical advantages of homogeneous catalysis with the practicality of heterogeneous systems. In these systems various substances are used as solid supports to immobilize active catalyst components. The solid supports explored include silica, alumina, carbon, polymers, zeolites and clay. Among these, Montmorillonite clay, a natural, abundant, and low-cost 2D layered silicate, is one of the most intensively explored catalytic materials in heterogeneous catalysis due to its cation exchange capacity, swelling ability, low cost and eco-friendliness. Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are a class of porous materials that offer tremendous synthetic applications due to their tunable structures, huge surface areas, and diverse functionalities. The unique properties of montmorillonite synergise with the MOFs to create stable and reusable hybrid materials. The montmorillonite matrix physically reinforces the MOF structure, boosting its thermal and chemical stability against harsh reaction conditions. The high-surface-area support of Montmorillonite successfully addresses the inherent limitations of pure MOFs. In the present paper, the synthesis and application their of some new N-heterocyclic compounds catalysed by montmorillonite supported palladium catalysts, including those involving in MOFs were discussed.

AS8. MOF-Driven Efficient Gas Storage & Advanced Separation

Kunsoth Pravalika, Marsakola Annapoorna

*TGTWRD&PG (W)College Shadnagar, Rangareddy District, T.S.
pravalikakunsoth2004@gmail.com, annapurnamarsakola1201@gmail.com*

Abstract: Metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) have emerged as one of the most versatile classes of porous crystalline materials for advanced gas storage and separation applications. Constructed from metal ions or clusters bridged by organic linkers, MOFs offer extraordinary surface areas, tailorable pore sizes, and chemically adjustable internal environments. These structural advantages enable exceptionally high adsorption capacities for gases such as hydrogen, methane, and carbon dioxide, positioning MOFs as promising candidates for clean energy storage and carbon-mitigation technologies. For gas separation, MOFs demonstrate significant potential in discriminating between molecular species with similar sizes or properties, enabling efficient separations such as CO₂/N₂, CO₂/CH₄, H₂/CH₄, and challenging olefin–paraffin mixtures.

Flexible or “breathing” MOFs further provide dynamic structural responses that enhance selective uptake under specific conditions. Hybrid materials, such as MOF–polymer composites and MOF-based mixed-matrix membranes, are gaining traction as promising pathways to bridge laboratory performance with real-world implementation. Continued advances in computational modelling, high-throughput screening, and green synthetic strategies are accelerating the discovery of robust frameworks optimized for targeted gas storage and separation tasks. Collectively, these developments reaffirm MOFs as strategically important materials for achieving sustainable, high-efficiency gas handling technologies.

Keywords: metal–organic frameworks, MOFs, gas storage, gas separation, adsorption, porosity, CO₂ capture, hydrogen storage, selective sorption, membrane technology.

Efficient Gas Storage And Separation With Advanced Metal Organic Frameworks

References: Li, J.-R.; Kuppler, R. J.; Zhou, H.-C. “Selective Gas Adsorption and Separation in Metal–Organic Frameworks.”*Chemical Society Reviews* 2009, 38, 1477–1504.

AS9. Synergistic Bimetallic MOFs for Sustainable Ibuprofen Remediation

Pavushetti Soumya

TGTWRD&PG (W) COLLEGE, SHADNAGAR.

Email id: soumyapavushetti@gmail.com

Abstract: “When Medicines become pollutants, Metal–Organic Frameworks become the cure”. In the modern era of rapid technological advancement, human dependence on machinery has dramatically increased, resulting in reduced physical activity and a rise in lifestyle-related disorders such as chronic body pain, muscle stiffness, headaches, and fatigue. While aspirin was once widely used to manage these ailments, its allergic reactions and intolerance at higher doses have shifted global preference toward ibuprofen, a more effective and well-tolerated nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID). Ibuprofen is now extensively consumed to treat pain, fever, menstrual cramps, cold, flu symptoms, swelling, and inflammation, offering broad therapeutic benefits in a single, easily accessible medication. Beyond human health, a significant global issue arises from ibuprofen’s environmental persistence. The human body metabolizes it only partially, causing a considerable portion to be excreted unchanged through urine. Additional contamination stems from improper disposal of expired medicines, effluents from pharmaceutical industries, hospital wastewater, and sewage sludge applied to agricultural fields. Conventional wastewater treatment plants are not equipped to eliminate pharmaceuticals like ibuprofen due to its high solubility, chemical stability, and poor biodegradability. As a result, ibuprofen persists as an emerging pollutant in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, where it contributes to aquatic toxicity, inhibited growth and reproduction in organisms, enzyme disruption, hormonal imbalance, bioaccumulation, and detrimental effects on soil microbial communities. Chronic exposure through contaminated water also raises human health concerns - heart attack & liver effects.

To address this challenge, Metal–Organic Frameworks (MOFs) have emerged as highly promising materials due to their exceptional porosity, tunable structures, and functional groups that enable adsorption, catalytic degradation, and transformation of ibuprofen into secondary molecules. While single-metal MOFs such as Zr-MOFs, Cu-MOFs, and Fe-MOFs have demonstrated significant capability, analytical techniques including HPLC, UV–Vis, and NMR are essential for precise detection of ibuprofen and its degradation pathways.

Recent research emphasizes the enhanced performance of bimetallic MOFs—such as Zr–Fe and Cu–Fe—where synergistic metal interactions improve catalytic efficiency, adsorption capacity, and recyclability. These frameworks can achieve up to 70–90% regeneration efficiency, making them more sustainable and cost-effective. However, Ibuprofen degradation often yields intermediate by-products—including 4-isobutylacetophenone, aromatic fragments, and organic acids—that may possess equal or greater toxicity than the parent compound. Although aliveluallc MOFs can convert portions of these intermediates into value-added products such as fuels. Therefore, achieving complete degradation into non-toxic end products remains an essential goal for advancing MOF-based environmental remediation.

AS10. Nano-enabled MOFs solutions for eco-friendly air and water purification

Ch. Snehalatha Reddy¹, K. Narender²

Department of Physics, Government Degree College, Wardhannapet, Warangal, Telangana state¹

Department of Physics, Government Degree College, Huzurabad, Dist. Karimnagar Telangana state²

Abstract: Nano-enabled solutions for eco-friendly air and water purification presents an innovative approach to achieving sustainable environmental purification using nanotechnology-driven methods. This method combines the extraordinary capabilities of nanomaterials with intelligent design principles to create a comprehensive platform capable of addressing one of the most critical challenges of pollution of air and water resources in modern civilization. This paper focuses on developing a new generation of purification systems that are not only more efficient than existing technologies but are also environmental friendly, energy-efficient, self regenerative and capable of long-term autonomous operation. Various prototypes utilizing nanomaterials such as metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), quantum dots, and nano-zeolites have shown remarkable performance in degrading pollutants and pathogens. For instance, hybrid systems combining photo catalytic nanomaterials with carbon-based adsorbents can achieve near-complete degradation of organic dyes and microbial deactivation under visible light irradiation. Similarly, air filters enhanced with silver and copper nanoparticles exhibit superior antimicrobial efficiency compared to conventional high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filters. These results have encouraged further exploration into scalable production, cost reduction, and safety assessment of nanomaterials for widespread environmental applications. Functionalized nanomaterials with exceptional surface reactivity, large surface area, and catalytic efficiency are helpful to capture, degrade, or neutralize contaminants. These materials include photo catalytic nanoparticles such as titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and zinc oxide (ZnO), adsorptive materials like graphene oxide and activated carbon nanotubes, and antimicrobial agents such as silver and copper nanoparticles. Each of these components performs a specific purification role adsorption of heavy metals, oxidation of organic pollutants, decomposition of volatile compounds, and destruction of microbial pathogens. The combination of these nanostructures creates a synergistic effect, significantly enhancing purification performance across a wide range of pollutants.

Key words: Air Purification, Water Purification, Nanomaterial, Metal Oxides And Metal-Organic Frameworks

AS11. Catalysis and Environmental Remediation: Challenges and Strategies

Ganti Jyothi,

Department of Chemistry, Pingle Government College for Women(A), Hanamkonda,

Email: jyothipgcwa@gmail.com

Abstract: The escalating crisis of environmental pollution-ranging from industrial waste, persistent organic pollutants (POPs), and emerging contaminants (ECs) such as pharmaceuticals to pervasive atmospheric, aquatic, and lithospheric (soil) pollution – demands the urgent development of robust, energy-efficient, and sustainable remediation technologies. Catalysis stands as a fundamental cornerstone technology, facilitating the rapid and selective transformation of toxic and persistent pollutants (including NO_x, VOCs, heavy metal ions, and complex organic dyes) into benign substances through precise chemical pathways, often achieving complete mineralization.

This paper provides a critical review of the current sophisticated landscape of environmental catalysis, focusing particularly on the primary techno-economic challenges hindering the large-scale industrial adoption of catalytic methods and the resultant ingenious remediation strategies being developed to overcome them. Key challenges comprehensively include catalyst deactivation (e.g., thermal sintering, chemical poisoning, carbon deposition or coking), mass transfer limitations in multiphase reactor systems, lack of sufficient long-term stability under heterogeneous real-world conditions, and the unsustainable reliance on expensive platinum group metals.

Advanced strategies, such as the precise design of earth-abundant Single-Atom Catalysts (SACs) to maximize atomic efficiency and selectivity, the development of highly stable nanostructured materials (e.g., hybrid metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) and high-entropy alloys), and the integration of multi-functional catalytic systems (e.g., photo-electrocatalysis), are being pursued. Furthermore, advanced computational models such as Density Functional Theory (DFT) and Artificial Intelligence -based design are critically examined as essential pathways toward predicting active sites, optimizing reaction pathways, and ultimately ensuring the technical and commercial feasibility of catalytic remediation for a cleaner, more sustainable future.

Key words: Catalysis, Environmental Remediation, Single-Atom Catalysts (SACs), Catalyst Deactivation, AI, Density functional theory (DFT).

AS12. Metal Organic Frameworks for Diverse Applications

B. Venkata Chakravarthi*, V Namratha, Tula kavitha

Department of Chemistry, Satavahana University, Karimnagar Telangana, India

E-mail: bv.chakravarthi115@gmail.com

Abstract: Metal organic frame works or MOFs, have emerged as an extensive class of crystalline materials with ultrahigh porosity and enormous internal surface area, extending beyond 6000m²/g. These properties, together with the extraordinary degree of variability for both the organic and inorganic components their structures, make MOFs interest for potential applications in clean energy most significantly as storage media for gases such as hydrogen and methane and as high capacity adsorbents to meet various separation needs. Additional applications in membranes, thin film devices, catalysis, and biomedical imaging are increasingly gaining importance. On a fundamental level, MOFs epitomize the beauty of chemical structures and the power of combining organic and inorganic chemistry two disciplines often regarded as disparate. Since the 1990s, this area of chemistry has experienced an almost unparalleled growth, as evidenced by not only the sheer number of research. Although the number of review articles and monographs has also escalated in the last five years, we believe this thematic issue of chemical reviews, comprising the most of-to-date contributions from leading MOF researchers all over the world, is necessary to mark the progress made thus far in a comprehensive manner.

The scope of the volume ranges from topology analysis and molecular simulations to synthesis, from adsorptive and optical to ferroelectric properties, and from gas storage, separations, and catalysis to applications in biomedicine. As such, current researchers in the field alike. One of the hallmarks of MOFs is their topologically diverse and aesthetically pleasing structures, many of which are derived, from minerals nature.. To reverse-engineer the beautiful structures from nature, the first step is to understand the underlying geometric principles. O’Keeffe and Yaghi demonstrate such an approach by deconstructing crystal structures of MOFs into their underlying topological nets, thereby laying a foundation for the subsequent description and design of other MOF structures.

Key-words: Metal organic frame works, Biomedical imaging, organic chemistry, monographs, ferroelectric properties and crystal structure.

AS13. Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs): A review on MOFs Research Leading to the 2025 Nobel Prize in Chemistry

Natte Kavitha ^{a*}, T. Savithajyostna ^{b*}

^a *Dept of Chemistry, Govt. Degree College, Bhuplapally, Telangana-506169, India*

^b *Dept of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana-506001, India*

E-mail: kavithanatte2008@gmail.com; Savithajyostna@kakatiya.ac.in

Abstract: Metal–Organic Frameworks (MOFs) are an exceptional class of crystalline porous materials formed by the coordination of metal ions or clusters with organic ligands, creating highly ordered three-dimensional networks. Their significance was internationally recognized with the 2025 Nobel Prize in Chemistry, awarded to Susumu Kitagawa, Richard Robson, and Omar M. Yaghi for their pioneering contributions to the conception, design, and development of MOFs, which have reshaped modern materials chemistry. Early foundational work in the late 1980s and 1990s, particularly by Robson, demonstrated that metal–ligand self-assembly could generate stable porous architectures. Building on this, Kitagawa revealed the dynamic nature and reversible adsorption behavior of MOFs, highlighting their functional potential. Yaghi further revolutionized the field through reticular chemistry, enabling the rational design of robust and highly tunable frameworks such as MOF-5, characterized by extraordinarily high surface areas.

The unique structural modularity and porosity of MOFs have driven breakthroughs in numerous applications, including gas storage and separation, carbon dioxide capture, hydrogen storage, environmental remediation, catalysis, water harvesting, and biomedical delivery systems. By allowing precise control over pore dimensions and chemical functionality, MOFs facilitate highly selective molecular interactions. Collectively, the Nobel-recognized advances in MOF science provide powerful tools for addressing critical global challenges related to energy, environment, and sustainability, positioning MOFs as a cornerstone of future materials innovation.

AS14. Synthesis and electrochemical studies of $\text{Na}_3\text{CoCO}_3\text{PO}_4$ as cathode for aqueous rechargeable sodium ion batteries

H. Manjunatha^{a,*}, K. Shiprath^b, S. Janardhan^a, K. Venkata Ratnam^a

^a*Electrochemical Energy and Sensor Research Lab (EESRL), Department of Chemistry, GITAM School of Science,*

GITAM (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru Campus, Bengaluru 562163 Karnataka, India

^b*Neocell Industries Pvt. Ltd, Andheri (E), Mumbai, Maharashtra 400072, India*

Abstract: Aqueous rechargeable sodium-ion batteries (ARSBs) have received much attention due to their low cost, the vast abundance of sodium, and the possible application for a smart grid-scale energy storage system. Here, we report the synthesis of $\text{Na}_3\text{CoCO}_3\text{PO}_4$ (NCCP), a cathode material for ARSBs by a low-temperature ionothermal method using deep eutectic solvent mixture and investigated its electrochemical performance. The physical characterization of the synthesized material was done using X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, energy-dispersive X-ray analysis, thermogravimetry analysis and differential thermal analysis to evaluate crystal size, structure, elemental composition and morphology. The crystallite size calculated from the most intensive peak at ($2\theta = 32.30$) of the XRD pattern by using the Scherrer equation is found to be ~ 29 nm and the same is confirmed by SEM analysis. The electrochemical behaviour of $\text{Na}_3\text{CoCO}_3\text{PO}_4$ in 2 M Na_2SO_4 was studied using cyclic voltammetry, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, and galvanostatic charge-discharge techniques. The study revealed that at high current rates, the cathode material, $\text{Na}_3\text{CoPO}_4\text{CO}_3$ exhibited excellent electrochemical performance. The full cell $\text{NaTi}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3/2$ M $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Na}_3\text{CoPO}_4\text{CO}_3$ shows an initial charge and discharge capacity of 177.38 mAh g^{-1} and 126.17 mAh g^{-1} at C/10 rate with better capacity retention over 100 cycles. This discharge capacity is almost close to the theoretical capacity of the material i.e. 189.5 mAh g^{-1} . Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is applied to study the NCCP which is a useful technique to distinguish the mechanism of Na-insertion/de-insertion process, such as charge transfer R_{ct} , solid state diffusion like Warburg Z_w , double layer capacitance and exchange current I_0 etc. All the kinetic parameters are obtained by simulating the equivalent circuit model with experimental EIS spectra. Important kinetic parameters like diffusion coefficient D_{Na^+} shows a minima at potentials corresponding to CV peak potentials.

AS15. Smart Drug Delivery Systems: Harnessing Physiochemical Triggers for Controlled Release.

M. Balaraju

Department of Chemistry, Pingle Government College for Women(A), Waddepally, Hanamkonda Email: balumacharla2012@gmail.com

Abstract: The pursuit of highly effective and safe therapeutic regimens has driven significant innovation in drug delivery.¹ Conventional drug administration often suffers from poor bioavailability, systemic toxicity, and sub-optimal therapeutic efficacy due to non-specific distribution.² Smart Drug Delivery Systems (SDDS) represent a paradigm shift, offering precise control over the timing, rate, and location of drug release in response to specific internal or external stimuli.³ This review examines the design principles and biomedical applications of SDDS that harness physiochemical triggers. Internal stimuli, which naturally arise from pathological states, include alterations in pH (common in tumor microenvironments and lysosomes), elevated temperature (associated with inflammation or hyperthermia), and changes in redox potential (glutathione concentration difference between intracellular and extracellular spaces). External, remotely-controlled triggers, such as light (UV/Near-Infrared), magnetic fields, and ultrasound, offer non-invasive and precise activation of the delivery mechanism.⁴ Key systems discussed include pH - responsive polymers, thermosensitive hydrogels, redox-cleavable nanocarriers, and photoactivated liposomes. By leveraging the difference between healthy and diseased tissues, or by utilizing external energy sources, these smart systems ensure that the therapeutic payload is released exactly when and where it is needed, minimizing off-target side effects and maximizing drug concentration at the diseased site.⁵ The successful translation of these trigger-responsive platforms holds immense potential for personalized medicine, particularly in the treatment of chronic diseases, cancer, and infectious diseases.

Keywords: Smart Drug Delivery Systems (SDDS), Controlled Release, Targeted Drug Delivery, Physiochemical Triggers, Stimuli-Responsive Systems, Nanocarriers (or Nanotechnology), pH-Responsive

AS16. Synthesis of sulfonated sustainable activated carbon catalysts from Gum Arabic Tree Seed Shell biomass for glycerol esterification

T. Jagadish*

Department of H&S (Chemistry), CVR College of Engineering, Hyderabad, 501510, India

Corresponding author: E-mail: jagadish.total23@gmail.com

Abstract: Glycerol, the primary byproduct of biodiesel, has been produced at a higher rate globally due to its benefits and features. Glycerol has undergone a number of chemical transformations, including hydrogenolysis, selective oxidation, decomposition, dehydroxylation acetylation, dehydration, carboxylation, and selective oligomerisation, synthesis gas production through reforming, esterification, and etherification. Because the byproducts of these reactions can be utilized as oxygenated additives for fuels like diesel and biodiesel, concluding an environmentally and financially appealing production cycle, glycerol conversion by esterification and etherification is especially intriguing. This use is another way to cut down on excess glycerol produced during the production of biodiesel, preventing issues for both biodiesel refineries and the glycerol market and economy. Additionally, using glycerol as a substitute raw material reduces the reliance on oil sources that are currently used to make fuel additives. The mono-, di-, and tri- acetates of glycerol that result from the esterification of glycerol with acetic acid are referred to as acetin. Here in this research, acid biochar catalysts were synthesized with Gum Arabic Tree seed shells as feedstock and varying activation temperatures in an attempt to examine whether acidity is correlated with activity. These catalysts were examined for glycerol esterification and determined glycerol conversion rate and selectivity towards monoacetin, diacetin, and triacetin under similar reaction conditions, and their physicochemical characteristics were carefully correlated with their intrinsic catalytic properties.

Fig.1. Biochar catalytic activity performance

References

- [1] T. Jagadish, M. Parusha Ramudu, Journal of molecular liquids. 424 (2025) 127039

AS17. Synthesis and Characterization of Iron Oxide Nano particles via Green Synthesis Technique

Shanmukhi Jyothi.D¹., Srikanth.K.¹, Bhaavaanjali.P.

Government Degree College(W), Hussainialam, Hyderabad.

Abstract: Iron oxide nanoparticles (NPs) have a bright future. They may be exploited as a suppository transport vector as well as in the treatment of illnesses and microbial pathogenesis. Additionally, they can eliminate tenacious dyes and serve as a substitute for cleaning up environmental toxins. The green synthesis process uses a variety of sources, including microorganisms, plants, and other biological products that serve as stabilizing and reducing agents. The process of bio-mediated nanoparticle production is candid. All that needs to be done is combine the necessary quantity of metal salt with plant extract, and the reaction will finish at room temperature in a matter of minutes to several hours. As a reducing agent, the metallic salt solution can produce the pertinent nanoparticles. Because it is less expensive, non-hazardous, and environmentally benevolent, the green synthesis process for nanoscale is employed all over the world. The investigation of the green produced Iron Oxide NPs' antibacterial and degrading activity is the innovative aspect of this work. The iron oxide nanoparticles used in this work were made from Ficus palmata leaves using a green synthesis method. Iron Oxide NP's peaks were observed between 230 and 290 nm which were confirmed by UV-Vis, and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy investigation revealed that several groups were involved in stabilization and reduction. The results showed that light had the maximum photo thermal activity, which was about four times higher than the control. Additionally, we gauged Iron Oxide NPs' capacity for photocatalysis alongside methylene orange. The results showed that after 90 minutes in the presence of continuous light, nearly total corrosion was seen. Every test was run in triplicate. Using Excel and Graph Pad (V.5.0), the P-test ($P < 0.5$) was applied to all the da

AS18. Novel C-4 Sulfenylated Pyrazoles as α -amylase inhibitors: Insights from *in Silico* and *in vitro* studies

Deepak Wadhwa^a, Jyoti^b

^a Assistant Professor, Department of Chemistry, Chaudhary Ranbir Singh University, Jind on deputation from Chaudhary Bansi Lal University, Bhiwani

^b Assistant Professor, Department of Chemistry, Chaudhary Ranbir Singh University, Jind
E-mail: deepak_chem08@cblu.ac.in

Abstract: The design and discovery of novel α -amylase inhibitors remain a promising strategy for the management of postprandial hyperglycemia associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus. In the present study, a new series of C-4 sulfenylated pyrazole derivatives was synthesized and evaluated for their inhibitory potential against α -amylase through integrated *in silico* and *in vitro* approaches. Molecular docking and dynamic simulations revealed high binding affinity of the synthesized compounds toward the α -amylase catalytic site, mediated primarily by hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions with key active-site residues. Among the tested candidates, several derivatives exhibited superior binding energies compared to the reference drug acarbose, indicating strong inhibitory potential. The *in vitro* enzyme inhibition assay further supported the computational findings, demonstrating concentration-dependent suppression of α -amylase activity with IC₅₀ values in the low micromolar range. Structure–activity relationship (SAR) analysis suggested that electron-withdrawing substituents on the sulfenyl moiety significantly enhanced biological activity. Overall, the combined computational and biochemical investigations highlight C-4 sulfenylated pyrazoles as promising lead molecules for the development of more effective α -amylase inhibitors, paving the way for future therapeutic optimization against diabetes-associated metabolic disorders.

AS19. Biomedical and Drug Delivery Applications of Biodegradable Polymers

J. Uma Rani, P. Jyothi

*Department of Chemistry
Government Degree College for Women, Gajwel,
Siddipet, Telangana, India
Email: janapatlauma@gmail.com; parvathijyothichem@gmail.com*

Abstract: The integration of biomedical science with materials chemistry has revolutionized modern drug delivery strategies. Conventional methods often face challenges such as poor bioavailability, lack of targeting, and systemic side effects. Recent developments in nanotechnology and polymer science have paved the way for smart and efficient delivery systems capable of releasing therapeutic agents at specific sites and controlled rates. Nano carriers such as liposomes, dendrimers, micelles, and polymeric nanoparticles enhance solubility, stability, and targeted delivery of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs.

Biodegradable polymers including chitosan, polylactic acid (PLA), and polycaprolactone (PCL) have gained attention for their excellent biocompatibility and ability to provide sustained drug release while minimizing toxicity. These materials degrade into non-toxic by-products, making them suitable for long-term biomedical use. Furthermore, stimuli-responsive systems triggered by changes in pH, temperature, enzymes, or magnetic fields offer adaptive and personalized therapeutic options.

Emerging research focuses on bio-based and eco-friendly carriers that align with the growing demand for sustainable healthcare materials. Such systems not only improve therapeutic outcomes but also address environmental and safety concerns associated with traditional synthetic polymers. This seminar presents an overview of current trends and future directions in biomedical and drug delivery applications, emphasizing the design of multifunctional carriers, challenges in large-scale production, and translation from laboratory to clinical practice. The discussion also highlights the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in developing next generation, patient-centered delivery systems.

Keywords: Drug delivery systems, Biodegradable polymers, Nano carriers, Smart materials, Biomedical applications.

AS20. Rapid Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles with Ginger Waste using Microwave Irradiation

C. Raghavender

Department of Chemistry, PG Center Wanaparthy, Palamuru University, Wanaparthy-509103, India

Abstract: In the present investigation, synthesis of gold nanoparticles (AgNPs) was carried out with microwave irradiation of AgNO₃ and the extract of ginger waste. Synthesized AgNPs were characterized by various techniques including UV-visible spectroscopy (UV-vis), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray powder diffraction (XRD), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The TEM images revealed that the nanoparticles were spherical in shape and the average particle size of the AgNPs was found to be approximately 6 ± 2 nm. The stability of silver nanoparticles was analyzed by zeta potential measurements. Further, silver nanoparticles exhibited excellent catalytic activity in reducing 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol in the presence of NaBH₄.

AS21. From Wonder Drugs to Global Threat: The Rise of Antibiotic-Resistant Superbugs

Sridhara Devi Nagulapally, Mummadi Narsing Rao, Gedam Sai Prasad

*Government Degree College (Sciences), Adilabad, Telangana, India
Email: nsridharadevi@gmail.com*

Abstract: Antibiotic resistance is a major concern to world health since "superbugs" that are resistant to many drugs make antibiotics less effective. These pathogens make therapy less effective, put a lot of stress on the healthcare system, and cost a lot of money and time. This study dwelves into the molecular causes of antibiotic resistance, the current burden and global spread of resistant superbugs, the primary challenges associated with containing resistance, and fresh perspectives and potential for research and therapeutic intervention. A thorough search on peer-reviewed publications, reviews, and reports published in the last 10 to 15 years. Studies pertinent to resistance mechanisms, epidemiology, therapeutic breakthroughs, and policy initiatives were incorporated. Resistance develops by enzymatic drug degradation, target alteration, efflux pumps, and horizontal gene transfer. Environmental factors, overuse of antibiotics in medicine and agriculture, and a lack of progress in developing new drugs all speed up resistance around the world. Recent progress includes novel approaches to identify antibiotics, new treatments including bacteriophages and antimicrobial peptides, and stronger systems for responsible use of antibiotics. However, regulatory issues and economic disincentives make it challenging to generate and employ new antimicrobials. Antibiotic resistance is still a complicated and evolving threat which demands a coordinated response involving scientific research, clinical practice, and changes to legislation. To combat the spread of super bugs and keep existing and new antimicrobial medicines working, we need to keep collaborative efforts worldwide and be ethical stewards.

Keywords: antibiotic resistance, superbugs, antimicrobial stewardship, bacteria that are resistant to more than one medicine, alternative therapies, global health, and new antibiotics

AS22. Development and Validation of an LC–MS/MS Method for Trace-Level Nitrosamine Analysis in Mexiletine Formulations

Prasanth Katakam, Bharat T. Kumar*

Department of Chemistry, School of Applied Sciences and Humanities, Vignan's Foundation for Science Technology and Research, Vadlamudi - 522213, Andhra Pradesh, India.

e-mail: drbkt_sh@vignan.ac.in

Abstract: Since 2018, pharmaceutical items must have regulated genotoxic targeted nitrosamine impurity levels for quality and safety. This work developed and validated a sensitive and robust analytical approach to quantitatively identify seven minor nitrosamines at low concentrations in mexiletine formulation. Gradient elution at 0.5 mL/min created mobile phases A and B from 0.1% formic acid in water and methanol, respectively. Chromatographic separation was obtained with a 40°C-maintained Inertsil ODS C18 column (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm). The procedure was verified to ICH and USP <1225> standards. This study shows superior accuracy (95.3-104.8%) and linearity ($R^2 > 0.999$). The mexiletine LC-MS/MS method is important because it uses a systematic, statistically optimized method development procedure to assure robustness, accuracy, and dependability. This approach may be applied to mexiletine capsules and other drug ingredients and goods under the minimally necessary method optimization circumstances, according to the study.

References:

1. D. M. Milenovic and Z. B. Todorovic, 'Development and application of a validated HPLC method for the analysis of dissolution samples of mexiletine hydrochloride capsules', *Journal of the Serbian Chemical Society*, vol. 75, no. 7, pp. 975–985, 2010, 10.2298/JSC090728065M.
2. International Council for Harmonisation of technical requirements for pharmaceuticals for human use ICH harmonised guideline assessment and control of DNA reactive (mutagenic) impurities in pharmaceuticals to limit potential carcinogenic risk M7(R2).

AS23. Ultra-Sensitive and Green LC-MS/MS Method for Trace-Level Determination of Nitrosamine Drug Substance-Related Impurities in the Anti-Diuretic Drug Furosemide

Santhosh Kumar Ettaboina, Satyasree Nannapaneni*

Department of Chemistry, Vignan's Foundation for Science Technology & Research, Guntur - 522213, Andhra Pradesh, India.

*Correspondence Author *: Dr. Satyasree Nannapaneni (drnss_sh@vignan.ac.in)*

Abstract; Nitrosamine drug substance-related impurities (NDSRIs) have emerged as critical genotoxic contaminants requiring ultra-trace-level monitoring in pharmaceutical products. In this study, we developed an **ultra-sensitive, green, and robust LC-MS/MS method** for the simultaneous quantification of trace-level NDSRIs associated with **furosemide**, a widely used anti-diuretic drug. Method development focused on minimizing organic solvent consumption while enhancing detection sensitivity through optimized chromatographic separation and multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) transitions. A green mobile phase system containing reduced levels of acetonitrile and eco-friendly additives was employed to achieve efficient analyte ionization and reproducible retention. The method demonstrated excellent sensitivity with LOQs in the low- ng/mL range, along with strong linearity ($R^2 > 0.999$), precision, accuracy, and solution stability. Validation was performed according to ICH M10 guidelines, confirming the method's suitability for routine quality control and risk-assessment studies. Overall, this environmentally conscious, high-performance LC-MS/MS workflow provides a reliable tool for monitoring nitrosamine impurities in furosemide drug products, supporting enhanced patient safety and regulatory compliance.

References:

1. FDA. *Control of Nitrosamine Impurities in Human Drugs – Guidance for Industry*. U.S. Food and Drug Administration, 2023.
2. N. Sultana, S. Gogineni, *Chem. Res. Toxicol.*, 2024 16;37(9), 1456-1483.

AS24. Synthesis, characterizations, and biological evaluations of 2-(phenyl ((1- phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)methyl)amino) benzenesulfonamide derivatives

Tula Kavitha, V. Namratha*

* Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Satavahana University, Malkapur Road, Chinthakunta, Karimnagar-505002, TG.
Email: namrathav69@gmail.com

Abstract: Using click chemistry, a novel series of 2-(phenyl((1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)methyl)amino)benzenesulfonamide derivatives (**6a–l**) were created, and spectroscopic methods were used to characterize their structural makeup. Using hydroxyl radical scavenging (HRS) and 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) tests, the antioxidant activity was assessed. Absorbance at 517 nm was measured after test solutions were incubated with radical-generating agents to calculate the percentage of inhibition in comparison to controls. With *ciprofloxacin* as a reference medication, antibacterial qualities were assessed using a modified agar well diffusion method against Gram-positive (*Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella Typhi*) organisms. *Fluconazole* served as the standard in the disc diffusion test of antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*. The results of experiments were supported by molecular docking studies that investigated ligand–protein interactions.

Keywords: Click chemistry; 1,2,3-triazole derivatives; benzenesulfonamide; antioxidant activity; Antimicrobial activity; molecular docking studies.

AS25. Exploring the extract of *Embelia ribes*' berries for its antitumor properties

Guruva Reddy Pasam,^{1,2} Sanjeev Sharma,¹ Srinivas Nerella,^{1,2}

¹Department of Chemistry, Om Sterling Global University, Hisar, Haryana, India

²Natural products Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Government Degree College, Wardhannapet, Warangal Dist, Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana, India-506313

Embelin (2,5-dihydroxy-3-undecyl-1,4-benzoquinone) is the major bioactive constituent isolated from the fruits of *Embelia ribes* Burm., a medicinal plant widely used in traditional Ayurvedic medicine. Chemically, embelin is a para-benzoquinone with a long alkyl side chain, conferring redox activity and membrane affinity (Gowda et al., 2009). Pharmacological studies have demonstrated that embelin possesses antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, and anticancer properties. Notably, embelin acts as a small-molecule inhibitor of X-linked inhibitor of apoptosis protein (XIAP), thereby inducing apoptosis in various cancer cell lines (Nikolovska-Coleska et al., 2004). It has also shown antihyperglycemic effects in experimental diabetic models through modulation of oxidative stress and glucose metabolism (Mahendran & Badami, 2011). Although embelin exhibits promising preclinical efficacy, its poor solubility and bioavailability limit clinical application, necessitating further research into formulation strategies and structural optimization.

Herein, we report the phytochemical analysis and anticancer activity of methanol and chloroform fractions of *Embelia ribes*' seeds. A total of three phytochemicals were identified in methanol fraction and whereas a total of four phytochemicals were identified in chloroform fraction. Both the fractions have shown good to moderate antitumor property in MTT *invitro* assay against four human cancer cell lines with IC₅₀ values ranging from 8-12μM

References

1. Gowda, D. V., et al. (2009). Antioxidant activity of embelin. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 71, 635–639.
2. Nikolovska-Coleska, Z., et al. (2004). Embelin as a potent inhibitor of XIAP. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 47, 2430–2440.
3. Mahendran, S., & Badami, S. (2011). Antidiabetic activity of embelin from *Embelia ribes*. *Biomedicine & Preventive Nutrition*, 1, 25–31.

AS26. Design, Synthesis and DNA Interaction Studies of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) Complexes with 5-Methyl-o-anisidine Schiff Bases

K. Jagadesh babu

*Department of Chemistry, Government Degree College, Parkal, Hanumakonda(Dist),
Telangana-506 164, India.*

Email: kjagadeshbabu@gmail.com

Abstract: Novel 5-methyl-o-anisidine Schiff bases $L^1(2-(4\text{-fluorobenzylidene})-2\text{-methoxybenzylamine})$ and their binary Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes were synthesized. The structures of all the compounds have been discussed on the basis of elemental analysis, FT-IR, NMR, UV-Visible, ESI-Mass, TGA, and ESR. Based on the analytical and spectral data a square planar geometry has been assigned to all complexes in which the Schiff bases act as monobasic bidentate ligands, coordinating through the azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atom. DNA binding ability of these complexes was studied on CT-DNA by using UV-Vis absorption, fluorescence and viscometer. DNA cleavage ability of the complexes was examined on pBR322 DNA by using gel electrophoresis method. All the DNA binding studies reveal that they are good intercalators. The bioefficacy of the ligands and their complexes was examined against the growth of bacteria and fungi in vitro to evaluate their antimicrobial potential. The screening data revealed that the complexes showed more antimicrobial activity than the corresponding free ligands.

AS27. Synthesis, Characterization, and Thermal Decomposition of Cu(II), Co(II), and Ni(II) Schiff Base Complexes for Metal Oxide Nanoparticle Formation

Satyanarayana Kandala

*Department of Chemistry, Government Degree college, (A), Narsampet
Email: Satyanarayanakandal@gmail.com*

Abstract: Novel Cu(II), Co(II), and Ni(II) complexes were synthesized using a Schiff base ligand (L1) derived from 3-formylchromone and aminomethylpyridines. The ligand coordinates to the metal ions through O and N donor atoms, exhibiting tetradentate or hexadentate binding modes. The complexes were thoroughly characterized using elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurements, infrared spectroscopy, UV–Visible spectroscopy, and ^1H NMR studies. Elemental analysis confirmed a 1:2 metal-to-ligand stoichiometry.

The thermal stability and decomposition pathways of the L1 complexes were examined using thermogravimetric (TG/DTG) analysis under a nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. The study highlights the successful use of these complexes as precursors for the preparation of CuO, CoO, and NiO nanoparticles through solid-state thermal decomposition. The resulting metal oxide nanoparticles were characterized for their crystalline phases by X-ray diffraction (XRD), while their morphology and elemental composition were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX).

Keywords: Schiff base Metal Complexes, 3-formyl chromone, Thermogravimetric Analysis (TG/DTG), Metal Oxide Nanoparticles, XRD, SEM.

AS28. Synthesis and in-vitro screening of Novel 1, 2, 3- Triazole Benz imidazole hybrids

G. Manasa, Ch. Sunitha

*Department of Chemistry, Vaagdevi Degree
and PG College, Kishanpura, Hanamkonda, T.S., India
Vaagdevi Engineering college, Bollikunta, Warangal, T.S., India
Email: manasaguttikonda16@gmail.com*

Abstract: Herein, we report the Synthesis of Benz imidazole thiazolidine conjugates using copper catalyzed azide alkyne cycloaddition. Firstly, (4-methyl 1H-benzo [d] imidazole 2-amine is subjected to N-alkylation using 3-bromo prop1-yne, next step involves the synthesis of 5-(1-prop-2-yne-1-yl) benzimidazole via. Knoevenagel condensation. Finally, the synthesized compounds were screened for in vitro anti-cancer activity against MCF-7, MDA-MB-468 human breast cancer cells. The synthesized analogues demonstrated significant anticancer activity at micromolar levels. MDS studies revealed that benzene and benzimidazole rings interacted well with various biological relevant targets through non- covalent interactions.

Scheme:

i) 3-bromo prop1- yne ii) Thiazolidine 2,4-dione iii) CuI, ArN₃ THF, RT 4hr

References:

1. B.S. Chhikara, K. Parang. Global Cancer Statistics 2022: the trends projection analysis. *Chem. Biol. Lett.* 2023, 10 (1), 451.
2. M. Abotaleb, P. Kubatka, M. Caprnda et.al. Chemotherapeutic agents for the treatment of metastatic breast cancer: An update. *Biomed. Pharmacother.* 2018, 101, 458-477.
3. A. Remesh. Toxicities of anticancer drugs and its management. *Int. J. Basic Clin. Pharmacol.* 2012, 1(2), 2319-2003.
4. X. Liang, Q. Wu, S. Luan, Z. Yin, C. He, L. Yin, Y. Zou, Z. Yuan, L. Li, X. Song, M. He. A comprehensive review of topoisomerase inhibitors as anticancer agents in the past decade. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 2019, 171, 129 168.
5. Y.J. Guo, W.W. Pan, S.B. Liu, Z.F. Shen, Y. Xu, L.L. Hu. ERK/MAPK signalling pathway and tumorigenesis. *Exp. Ther. Med.* 2020, 19(3), 1997-200

AS29. Design and EGFR Targeting of a Furan-Containing Imidazolium Salt for Breast Cancer Therapy: Synthesis, Anticancer Activity, Docking, and DFT Insights

Prabhakar Myadaraveni, Rambabu , Ramu Guda, , Devendar B, Mamatha Kasula*

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal, 506009, India

**Corresponding author: mamatakasula@gmail.com*

Abstract: We report the synthesis of a new series of furan-substituted imidazolium salts as N-heterocyclic carbene (FNHC) precursors and their evaluation in terms of electronic properties, epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) tyrosine kinase inhibition, and anticancer potential. The FNHC derivatives exhibited moderate inhibitory activity against EGFR, with an IC_{50} value of $0.99 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{M}$, in comparison to the clinically used inhibitor erlotinib ($IC_{50} = 0.44 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{M}$). In vitro cytotoxicity studies revealed IC_{50} values of $8.19 \pm 0.39 \mu\text{M}$ against MCF-7 cells and $9.58 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{M}$ against MDA-MB-231 cells, while demonstrating lower cytotoxicity toward normal MCF-10A breast epithelial cells ($IC_{50} = 16.33 \pm 0.30 \mu\text{M}$), suggesting a moderate degree of selectivity. Molecular docking studies performed with the EGFR kinase domain (PDB ID: 4HJO) indicated favorable binding of FNHC within the hinge region, stabilized by hydrogen-bonding interactions with Lys704 and hydrophobic contacts involving Met769. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations showed a HOMO–LUMO energy gap of 4.06 eV and a relatively high electrophilicity index ($\omega = 10.26 \text{ eV}$), offering qualitative insight into the electronic features of the FNHC scaffold. Taken together, these combined biochemical, computational, and cytotoxicity results suggest that FNHC represents a promising structural lead for further optimization rather than a fully developed EGFR-targeted anticancer candidate.

Fig: The optimized geometrical structures of the synthesized FNHC.

AS30. Influence of Surface Properties and Metal Interactions in ZnO / Ni / Pd Catalysts for Furfural Aldol Condensation

Jeedi Suman^a, S. Jyothi^{a*}

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal—506009, Telangana, India

Abstract: The manuscript describes the key aspects of ZnO/Ni/Pd Oxide prepared by different methods NH₃ method and co-precipitation methods using either NH₃ base Alkali solution or solution of NH₃, affording high conversion and selectivity values in aldol condensation of furfural with acetone. The structure, composition and acid-base properties of ZnO/Ni/Pd oxides were described by using of TGA, XRD, N₂-adsorption, TPD- NH₃/CO₂ and *in-situ* diffuse reflectance spectroscopy and correlated with the catalytic performance of a series of ZnO/Ni/Pd oxide catalysts. Along with the impact of specific surface area and basicity on the furfural conversion, the conversion of furfural also increased with the increasing value of the edge of the UV-vis spectrum of ZnO/Ni/Pd oxide, reflecting ZnO/Ni/Pd interaction. We have introduced a simple method based on diffuse reflectance spectroscopy with the potential to predict furfural conversion over ZnO/Ni/Pd in an aldol condensation of furfural with melatonin.

Key Notes

ZnO oxides synthesised using the NH₃ method (ammonia base), the Co-precipitation method some % with NH₃ solution Prepare catalysts with high conversion and selectivity for aldol condensation.

AS31. Lawsone as a Precursor for Biologically potent Small Molecules

Vijaykumar Allam¹, Gavaji Brahmeshwari¹, Srinivas Nerella²

[†]Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal, India-506009

[‡]Natural products Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Government Degree College, Wardhannapet, Kakatiya University, Warangal, India-506313

Corresponding Author's Email: nerellasrinivas1@gmail.com

Abstract: Lawsone (2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone) is a naturally occurring naphthoquinone predominantly found in the leaves of *Lawsonia inermis* (henna) and other plant species. Structurally characterized by a naphthoquinone core with a hydroxyl substitution at the C-2 position, lawsone displays a rich redox chemistry that underlies its diverse biological activities (Tripathi & Mishra, 2011). The conjugated quinone system facilitates electron transfer reactions, which contribute to both its pigmentation properties and its bioactive profile (Khan et al., 2017). Lawsone's most recognized application is as a natural dye used in traditional body art and textile coloring, owing to its ability to form stable covalent bonds with keratin in skin and hair proteins (Rai et al., 2015). Beyond its chromophore function, a growing body of research has documented lawsone's antimicrobial, antifungal, antioxidant, and anticancer activities. The compound exhibits inhibitory effects against a spectrum of pathogenic bacteria and fungi, likely due to quinone-mediated oxidative stress and disruption of microbial cell integrity (Ali et al., 2018). Similarly, lawsone demonstrates free-radical scavenging activity in vitro, attributed to its phenolic hydrogen and redox cycling capability (Singh & Sharma, 2019).

Herein, we report lawsone bound heterocyclic molecules via Click protocol at ambient conditions and their anticancer studies. Vivaly, the synthesized molecules have shown significant anticancer activity against human cancer cell lines in MTT assay.

References

1. Ali, N., Zafar, S., & Shams, S. (2018). Antimicrobial activity of lawsone against human pathogenic microorganisms. *Journal of Natural Pharmaceuticals*, 9(1), 23–30.
2. Gupta, A., Kumar, S., & Singh, R. (2020). Cytotoxic and apoptotic effects of lawsone in human cancer cell lines. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 127, 110198.
3. Khan, M. R., Rizvi, W., & Sahreen, S. (2017). Chemical composition and antioxidant activity of henna (*Lawsonia inermis*) extracts. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 9(6), 42–51.
4. Patel, D. K., et al. (2016). Evaluation of genotoxicity and safety profile of lawsone. *Toxicology Reports*, 3, 784–791.

AS32. DNA Binding cleavage and microbial studies of 4 amino-5-substituted Aryl-1,2,4-Triazoles-3-Thione Derivatives and their chelates

Goranti Laxmana Rao

Department of H&S, DRK Institute of science and technology, Hyderabad-500043, Telangana, India.

Email: lakshman.gorantla@gmail.com

Abstract: 1,2,4-Triazoles have gained considerable importance in coordination chemistry due to their structural resemblance to pyrazole and imidazole. Their ability to coordinate through nitrogen and sulfur atoms makes them promising ligands for synthesizing metal complexes with significant biological activities. Organic compounds containing nitrogen and sulfur, along with their metal complexes, are known for antitumor, antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral properties. Thiosemicarbazone-based ligands exhibit versatile coordination through sulfur and nitrogen, enhancing their biological potential. The proposed research focuses on the synthesis, characterization, DNA binding/cleavage, microbial evaluation, and computational analysis of 4-amino-5-substituted aryl-1,2,4-triazole-3-thione derivatives and their metal chelates. The proposed work involves crystal growth, microbial studies, DNA interaction analysis, and computational evaluation (Mulliken charge distribution, dipole moments, binding energies, heats of formation, and HOMO–LUMO mapping). Experimental results will be supported by theoretical calculations

AS33. *Butea monosperma*-Mediated Silver Nanoparticles: Synthesis, Characterization, and Antimicrobial Activity

S Yuva raju

Department of Botany, PG Center Wanaparthy, Palamuru University, T.S. India

Abstract: Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) were synthesized using a green method in which *Butea monosperma* acted as both the stabilizing and reducing agent, assisted by microwave irradiation. The resulting AgNPs had an average size of 11 ± 2 nm. The effects of AgNO₃ concentration, gum concentration, and reaction time on nanoparticle formation were systematically studied. Characterization was carried out using UV–Visible spectroscopy, FTIR, TEM, and powder XRD techniques. The synthesized AgNPs exhibited strong antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*. Overall, the findings demonstrate that the AgNPs possess significant antimicrobial properties.

AS34. Flexible MOFs for Selective Adsorption and Separation of Anions, Dyes, and Indicators in water

Sajal Khatua

*Department of Chemistry, GITAM, Hyderabad campus, Telangana-502329, India
E-mail: skhatua@gitam.edu*

Abstract: The present work focuses on the design and application of flexible Metal–Organic Frameworks (MOFs) for advanced separation processes. It provides a comprehensive overview of MOFs, emphasizing their classification, dynamic structural behaviour, and the phenomenon of single-crystal-to-single-crystal (SC–SC) transformations. Particular attention is given to the unique properties of flexible MOFs and their potential for multifunctional material development. A novel two-dimensional Zn-based flexible MOF is reported, exhibiting the ability to reversibly encapsulate a wide range of hazardous species including five toxic anions, dyes, and indicators from aqueous media under ambient conditions, while preserving its structural integrity. The resulting host-guest complexes exhibit unique colour change. They can be visually recognizable. Thus, the MOF offers a potential platform for anions, dyes and indicators recognition. Thus, it can be used as colorimetric sensor without using any spectroscopy methods. This work underscores the promising role of flexible MOFs in environmental remediation and molecular separation technologies.

AS35. Synthesis and Repurposing Evaluation of Raltegravir analogues as Potential Anticancer Agents

Sivakrishnaprasad Satram^{a,b}, Pushpendra Tiwari^b, Srinivas Nerella^{a,b*}

^a *Department of Chemistry, Government Degree College, Wardhannapet, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506313*

^b *Department of Chemistry, Mansarovar Global University, Sehore, M.P.-466001*

Abstract: Raltegravir is a clinically approved HIV-1 integrase inhibitor and has attracted interest as a scaffold for drug repurposing. In the present study, a series of raltegravir analogues was designed and synthesized to explore their potential anticancer activity. Structural modifications were introduced mainly on the heterocyclic core and side-chain regions of raltegravir. All compounds were characterized using ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR, LC-MS, and single-crystal X-ray diffraction for selected analogues. The synthesized analogues were evaluated for their in vitro cytotoxic activity against selected human cancer cell lines and murine breast carcinoma cell lines. Several compounds showed moderate to good antiproliferative effects compared to the parent molecule. Preliminary structure–activity relationship analysis indicated that specific substitutions play a key role in enhancing anticancer activity. These results suggest that raltegravir can serve as a useful lead structure for the development of new anticancer agents.

AS36. Thermodynamic properties of the binary mixtures of Ethyl phenyl ketone with Alkanediols at different temperatures.

M. Durga Bhavani^a, K. Narendra^{b,*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, V.R. Siddhartha School of Engineering College, SAHE University, Vijayawada- 520 007, Andhra Pradesh, India

^bDepartment of Physics, V.R. Siddhartha School of Engineering College, SAHE University, Vijayawada- 520 007, Andhra Pradesh, India

*Corresponding author: mopidevi1986@gmail.com

Abstract: The present investigation reports experimental values of density, ρ , and speed of sound, u , for binary liquid mixtures of Ethyl phenyl ketone (EzEt)+ Alkanediols {2-methoxyethanol (2-ME), or 2-ethoxyethanol (2-EE) } over the whole composition range at $T = (303.15, 308.15, 313.15 \text{ and } 318.15) \text{ K}$, and at atmospheric pressure (0.1MPa). Experimental data on densities and speeds of sound have been used to derive excess molar volume, V_m^E , excess isentropic compressibility, κ_s^E , excess molar isentropic compressibility, $K_{s,m}^E$, excess speed of sound, u^E , and excess isobaric thermal expansivity, α_p^E . Excess parameters were correlated by the Redlich-Kister polynomials. Excess partial molar volumes ($\bar{V}_{m,1}^E$ and $\bar{V}_{m,2}^E$) and their limiting values at infinite dilution ($\bar{V}_{m,1}^{0E}$ and $\bar{V}_{m,2}^{0E}$) have been calculated from the experimental density measurements and analytically obtained using Redlich-Kister polynomials. The results have been interpreted on the basis of strength and extent of intermolecular interactions prevalent in these mixtures.

Keywords: Ethyl phenyl ketone; Alkanediols; ultrasonic velocity; density; molar volume.

AS37. Design and Synthesis of Activated Carbon and Metal Organic Framework-based Composites for High-Performance Super Capacitors

P. Rajani, P. Swathi, K. Bhargavi, and K. Prabhakara Rao*

*New Generation Materials Lab (NGML), Department of Chemistry, School of Applied Science and Humanities, Vignan's Foundation for Science Technology and Research (VFSTR) (Deemed to be University), Vadlamudi-522 213, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India
rajani_puchakayala9@gmail.com and drkpr_sh@vignan.ac.in*

Abstract: The metal organic frameworks (MOFs) on activated carbon composite meld the advantages of each constituent—MOFs contribute their easily tunable pore architecture and high adsorption capacity, while activated carbon supplies mechanical strength and superior electrical conductivity.¹⁻⁴ In this connection, biomass-derived activated carbon was prepared by pre-carbonation, carbonation, and activation of coconut shell (ACCS).⁵ Activated carbon and metal-organic framework-based composites (Zn-BTMB@ACCS, Zn-Co-BTMB@ACCS, and Zn-Ni-BTMB@ACCS) were synthesized and successfully characterized. A typical three-electrode system was developed to measure the electrochemical performance of the composites (depicted in Fig. 1(a)). The electrochemical performance of the composites and the precursor MOF is shown in Fig. 1(b). The levels of all synthesized electrocatalysts surpass those of the precursor MOFs. This work offers a simple method for creating a high-performance metal-carbon hybrid super capacitor with many exposed active sites from bimetallic MOFs.

References:

1. K. Prabhakara Rao, M. Higuchi, K. Sumida J. Duan, S. Furakawa and S. Kitagawa, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **2014**, 53, 8225.
2. K. Prabhakara Rao, M. Higuchi, J. Suryachandram and S. Kitagawa, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*; **2018**, 140, 13786.
3. J. Suryachandram, R. Nagaraju, J. N. Behera, K Prabhakara Rao, *Inorg. Chem.* **2022**, 61, 14344.
4. J. Suryachandram, R. Nagaraju, and K Prabhakara Rao, *ACS Applied Energy.*; **2025**, 8, 5291.
5. K. Ching Lee, S. Chong, M. Lim. *Energies.* **2021**, 14, 4546.

AS38. Room-Temperature Ethanol Gas Sensing Performance of Lithium-Doped NiO Thin Films Prepared by Spray Pyrolysis

Rajesh. K

*Department of Physics, SRR Government Arts & Science Degree and PG College (A),
Karimnagar, Telangana, India
E-mail: rajeshbhu1234@gmail.com*

Abstract: Lithium-doped nickel oxide (Li:NiO) thin films were deposited on glass substrates using the spray pyrolysis technique and investigated for room-temperature ethanol gas sensing applications. X-ray diffraction analysis confirmed the formation of polycrystalline cubic NiO with slight lattice distortion due to Li incorporation. The films exhibited a uniform and porous surface morphology, which enhances gas diffusion and adsorption. Optical studies showed a marginal variation in the optical band gap arising from dopant-induced defect states. Gas sensing measurements revealed that Li-doped NiO thin films exhibit high sensitivity toward ethanol at room temperature, with a fast response time of 6 s and recovery time of 9 s, along with good repeatability and stability. The enhanced sensing performance is attributed to increased hole concentration, improved surface reactivity, and efficient charge carrier transport induced by Li doping. These results indicate that Li-doped NiO thin films prepared by spray pyrolysis are promising candidates for low-power, rapid ethanol gas sensing applications.

AS39. Podophyllotoxin Derivatives as Potential Drugs Against Cancer Treatment

Kalesha Saik,^a Vijaykumar Allam,^c Jyothi Prashanth^b, Ch. N. S. S. Pavan Kumar,^{a*} Srinivas Nerella^{c*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Vignan's Foundation for Science, Technology & Research, Guntur, A.P, India

^bDepartment of Physics, Kakatiya University, Warangal, India-506009

^cNatural products Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Government Degree College, Wardhannapet, Warangal Dist, Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana, India-506313

Corresponding author: nerellasrinivas1@gmail.com

Podophyllotoxin is a naturally occurring aryltetralin lignan isolated principally from the rhizomes and roots of *Podophyllum peltatum* and *Podophyllum hexandrum* (Hemscheidt & Halvorson, 2018). Structurally characterized by a tetracyclic core with multiple stereocenters, podophyllotoxin exhibits potent antimetabolic activity through reversible binding to tubulin, thereby inhibiting microtubule polymerization and arresting cell division at the metaphase stage of the cell cycle (Canel et al., 2000). Clinically, podophyllotoxin itself has been employed as a topical antiviral agent in the treatment of anogenital warts caused by human papillomavirus (HPV). Its ability to selectively disrupt the proliferation of infected epithelial cells underpins its therapeutic utility in dermatological applications (Feldman et al., 2006). Beyond direct use, podophyllotoxin has served as a lead compound in anticancer drug development. Semi-synthetic derivatives such as etoposide and teniposide were designed to improve pharmacokinetic profiles and reduce systemic toxicity; these analogues act primarily by inhibiting DNA topoisomerase II, leading to DNA strand breakage and apoptosis in rapidly dividing cancer cells (Cragg & Pezzuto, 2016; Noble et al., 1990).

Herein, we report a novel series of Schiff base derivatives of podophyllic acid hydrazides, designed from the aryltetralin lignan Podophyllotoxin, and evaluated for their anticancer and epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) inhibitory activities. Among the synthesized compounds, derivative **5i** exhibited outstanding cytotoxic potency with IC₅₀ values of 5.04 ± 0.34 μM against HeLa and 7.72 ± 0.34 μM against A549 cell lines, outperforming other analogs. Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations revealed that its superior bioactivity correlates strongly with key electronic and physicochemical parameters, including a small HOMO–LUMO gap (–2.10 eV), suggesting enhanced molecular reactivity and stability.

References

1. Canel, C., Moraes, R. M., Dayan, F. E., & Ferreira, D. (2000). Podophyllotoxin. *Phytochemistry*, 54(2), 115–120.
2. Cragg, G. M., & Pezzuto, J. M. (2016). Natural products as a vital source for the discovery of cancer chemotherapeutic and chemopreventive agents. *Medical Principles and Practice*, 25(Suppl. 2), 41–59.
3. Feldman, S. R., Hinds, G., & Fleischer, A. B. (2006). Topical therapies for the treatment of genital warts. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*, 54(3), 536–547.
4. Hemscheidt, T. K., & Halvorson, H. O. (2018). Podophyllotoxin and related lignans. *Annual Plant Reviews Volume 35: Plants and Cancer*, 235–263.

2025 NOBEL PRIZE IN CHEMISTRY

Omar M. Yaghi

**University of California,
Berkeley, USA**

Susumu Kitagawa

**Kyoto University,
Japan**

Richard Robson

**University of Melbourne,
Australia**

The Nobel Prize laureates in chemistry 2025 have created molecular constructions with large spaces through which gases and other chemicals can flow. These constructions, metal-organic frameworks, can be used to harvest water from desert air, capture carbon dioxide, store toxic gases or catalyse chemical reactions.

Figure 5. In 1999, Yaghi constructed a very stable material, MOF-5, which has cubic spaces. Just a couple of grams can hold as much gas as a football pitch.

Figure 3. In 1997, Kitagawa succeeded in creating a metal-organic framework that was intersected by open channels. These could be filled with different types of gas. The material could release these gases without its structure being affected.

Figure 2. Richard Robson was inspired by the structure of diamond, in which every carbon atom is linked to four others in a pyramid-like shape. Rather than carbon, he used copper ions and a molecule with four arms, each with a nitrile at the end. This is a chemical compound that is attracted to copper ions. When the substances were combined, they formed an ordered and very spacious crystal.

Government Degree College, Wardhannapet

MOFSF-2025 Brochure released by the Principal & Staff at GDC, Wardhannapet

MOFSF-2025 Brochure released by the Vice Chancellor & Registrar, Kakatiya University, Warangal

**Organized by
Department of Chemistry
Government Degree College, Wardhannapet
Kakatiya University, Telangana state, India-506313**